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Food Nutrition Security

Food Nutrition Security Cloud

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Report on exposure assessment tools and associated training materials

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1 Summary

Food may contain hazardous substances such as contaminants or residues from pesticides or food packaging materials. Food risk assessment requires various types of data (e.g., chemical concentrations, food consumption and health hazards). There are already some well-established datasets (e.g., in EFSA collections), but also emerging datasets (e.g., data from total diet studies) which can be very useful for food risk assessment analysis. Tools for food risk assessment which use this data also exist, but these require well-formatted input data. Data harmonization and data conversion are therefore essential steps in the assessment process. In addition, food risk assessment is complex and is constantly evolving, adopting more complex statistical approaches as the discipline develops. Therefore, it is useful to develop demonstrator software to facilitate understanding and guide different identified user groups including risk assessors and low-end-users.

Task 4.3 of the FNS-Cloud project aims to create e-services that enable two examples of user communities; low-end users (such as consumers or potential professional users that are not experts for TDS concept or exposure assessment) and researchers/risk assessors, to evaluate and visualize chemical food safety data (considered high-end users). Low-end users will be able to use concentration data from total diet studies (TDS) within the decision-making processes in their daily life, e.g., in the supermarket when purchasing foods. High-end users, e.g., risk assessors and researchers, will be able to use TDS or monitoring data for higher-tier more complex risk assessments. Specifically, the latter approach will use the probabilistic assessment with the Monte Carlo Risk Assessment (MCRA) tool.

With the tools and services being developed within FNS-Cloud there are five phases to this work split over WP4 (Use cases) and WP5 (Demonstrators), covering specification, implementation and testing (Task 4.3) and improvement and evaluation (in WP5). For each use case, demonstrator software has been developed.

In this report the training materials and user guides of these five demonstrators are outlined. Four demonstrators are using the exposure assessment tool MCRA and one demonstrator is based on a consumer app. The four demonstrators using MCRA are TDS-exposure harmonised, TDS-exposure German children to methylmercury, TDS-exposure Belgian adults to nickel and acute cumulative exposure to pesticides.

2 Introduction exposure assessment tools

For high-end users, the exposure assessment tool Monte Carlo Risk Assessment (MCRA-software) available in the cloud via mcra.rivm.nl was selected as the appropriate tool for four case studies developed by RIVM, WUR, UGent and BfR. For each case study demonstrator software and training materials were developed. MCRA is a web-based platform containing various models that users can use to assess the health risks for specific populations in various scenarios. MCRA is developed and used in various European projects and in a partnership with EFSA.

For the first MCRA case study a demonstrator was developed which performs probabilistic risk assessment using the data of TDS studies of three different countries (Germany, Belgium and The Netherlands). The data used is formatted in a harmonised way.

For the second MCRA case study a demonstrator was developed which performs probabilistic risk assessment regarding the exposure of German children to methylmercury. TDS data are combined with food consumption data, and the method is developed to address stratification of the calculations regarding region, season and food type (organic or not).

For the third MCRA case study a demonstrator was developed which performs probabilistic risk assessment regarding the exposure of Belgian children, adolescents, and adults to nickel. TDS data are combined with food consumption data.

For the fourth MCRA case study a demonstrator was developed which performs probabilistic risk assessment regarding the exposure of Dutch children to pesticides. EFSA monitoring data are combined with food consumption data. In this example, the focus is on cumulative exposure because different pesticides can have the same health effect and should therefore be combined in the risk assessment.

A fifth case study developed by PMT and BfR aims to develop a new low-end app to provide information about single chemicals and their contents in foods based on data of total diet studies.

The four MCRA case studies aim to improve the transparency of the data organisation and calculations, and to make these types of calculations available in future demonstrator software. Data providers will be asked to share their data in the FNS-Cloud, but many data owners of food consumption data are concerned about GDPR issues related to their data set(s).

3 MCRA exposure assessment tools

For high-end users, the exposure assessment tool Monte Carlo Risk Assessment (MCRA-software) available in the cloud via mcra.rivm.nl is selected as the appropriate tool for four case studies developed by RIVM, WUR, UGent and BfR. For each case study, demonstrator software is developed. In MCRA a demonstrator is called a standard action. In the following paragraphs a short description is provided of each case study. Also, the purpose of the demonstrator is given. For each demonstrator training materials are developed. A short description of the content of the training material is provided. Finally, information regarding user guidance describing the use of the tool and organisation of data is provided.

3.1 Demonstrator: TDS-exposure harmonised

3.1.1 Description and purpose of the exposure assessment tool

The MCRA exposure assessment tool includes the demonstrator 'TDS- long term dietary exposure and risk assessment'. This demonstrator was developed to show the importance of harmonised TDS data collection and how TDS of different countries or data providers can be used in a harmonised way. When data is organized in a harmonized way, it is relatively easy to link these data to the demonstrator. The output is provided using simple pie charts and tables. Furthermore, the data organisation is explained in detailed tables. This explanation will support the end-user in using the demonstrator with their own data. The demonstrator will be described in a hands-on exposure assessment training session during a TDS workshop organized jointly by the World Health Organization (WHO) and BfR in October 2022. For this workshop, RIVM will provide a training on exposure assessment using TDS data.

3.1.2 Training materials

The training materials to be used in this training session consists of two parts: the first part explains the use of the demonstrator and interpretation of the results of an exposure assessment. Within this there will be a demonstration as to how a user can upload own data files and use these data files in an exposure assessment. The second part identified what organization of the TDS data is needed to perform the exposure assessment. The training materials are included in the appendix to this Deliverable (see Appendix 1 and 2).

3.2 Demonstrator: TDS-exposure German children to methylmercury

3.2.1 Description and purpose of the exposure assessment tool

The second exposure assessment tool includes the MCRA standard action 'TDS-based long-term exposure and risk assessment of methylmercury for German children'. This is a simplified interface to conduct exposure and risk assessments in MCRA. The simplification strives to provide an easy application to support exposure and risk assessment workshops to allow participants first, easy calculations and data outputs. The standard action is derived from an example dataset of artificial methylmercury concentration data from a TDS and consumption data study of children in Germany. This dataset was used to develop and implement TDS functionalities in MCRA (described in Deliverable D4.3). These implementations have now been translated from the full action functionality in MCRA to a simplified training resource (standard action). In the standard action, exposure and risk assessments for different regions, seasons or production types are shown. It also

allows assessments for different consumer scenarios and selected foods, and for the lower bound or upper bound approach. The focus of the standard action is to become familiar with the specific data structure of a comprehensive TDS and the resulting options for analysis of the data with MCRA. The output is condensed to provide only essential information. Furthermore, supporting documentation is embedded into the interface for a better understanding of the applied data structure, underlying calculations and the provided output.

3.2.2 Training materials

The exposure assessment tool including this standard action will be applied in a hands-on exposure assessment training during a TDS workshop organized jointly by WHO and BfR in October 2022. The target group are several European and non-European WHO TDS Centers who register to learn the planning, conduction and evaluation steps of TDSs. Details on extent and content of the workshop are currently in planning.

Training material related to the standard action have been developed and are available in the attachment (see Appendix 3). They are divided into five sections and consist of a PowerPoint presentation and a handout for exercises. The first sections explain the concept of the standard action along with the connection to the full action functionalities of MCRA. The second section shows how to create a new standard action. Screenshot with explanatory notes guide the user through the creation steps. The third section introduces the standard action interface. Screenshots and notes explain how to find the documentation section and which setting options are available to conduct own calculations. The fourth and fifth section are the exercise and solution part of the training. The handout describes the related exercise. These are mainly compiled to show the users the possibilities of distinct regional, seasonal and production type specific exposure assessments. The artificial concentration data are especially adjusted to depict such differences. The solution sections show how to find the related results in the standard action output.

3.3 Demonstrator: TDS-exposure Belgian adults to nickel

3.3.1 Description and purpose of the exposure assessment tool

MCRA is a powerful platform to conduct exposure assessment as well as the risk assessment of different chemicals in food either via aggregated or TDS exposure studies. The purpose of this training is to introduce this platform to students and show them how can they perform actions (std) in MCRA. Of course, other related actions such as data preparation and formatting were aimed to demonstrate to the students. The available slides in the appendix were used to train the students under the training program entitled **food safety and risk analysis course in December 2021**. This training tool will be used for another course entitled **Quality assurance and risk analysis in agrifood chain in April 2022**. An additional purpose of the course was to provide the login access of the students to the MCRA. This makes MCRA available for them to conduct the assessment by their own.

3.3.2 Training materials

The provided slides (see Appendix 4) were used to show the process of conducting the risk assessment in MCRA. This was included the early step of creating the data, data preparation and formatting. And the goal was general preparation of data to be match with the MCRA framework. This was followed by explaining about the data coding (either concentration or consumption data) to be match and in order to make it possible for the risk assessor to conduct the best and most accurate calculation. Subsequently, creating the

standard (std) actions were explained and audiences learned how they can use this pre-defined action to obtain their required results. Performing the action, obtaining the results and results interpretations were other parts of this training.

3.4 Demonstrator: Acute cumulative exposure to pesticides

3.4.1 Description and purpose of the exposure assessment tool

The standard action 'Acute cumulative exposure to pesticides' performs probabilistic risk assessment regarding the exposure of Dutch children to pesticides. EFSA monitoring data are combined with food consumption data. In this example the focus is on cumulative exposure because different pesticides can have the same health effect and should therefore be combined in the risk assessment.

The retrospective exposure assessment of the nervous system used monitoring data from 2014, 2015 and 2016. The results, data used, and methodology are reported in a scientific report published on the EFSA Website in 2019 (Klaveren, 2019).

The tool can be used by Food Safety Authorities and industry companies to familiarize them with the concept of the risk of combined exposure to multiple pesticides (mixtures) using the MCRA software. The standard action is also used to give the end-users a better understanding of the output of the combined exposure assessment of multiple pesticides and how it can be used by Food Safety Authorities and industry companies in the context of guidance of the European Food Safety Authority.

3.4.2 Training materials

The first part of the training consists of an introduction and an overview of the concept of cumulative risk assessment of pesticides. This lecture is presented using PowerPoint slides (see Appendix 5).

In the second part the use of the standard action in MCRA is presented. In the standard action participants could choose country specific consumption data to perform the cumulative risk assessment (see Appendix 5). The use of the standard action was explained by using PowerPoint slides. Participants could simultaneously use the standard action and perform the calculations themselves.

In the PowerPoint presentation some attention was given to the format of the data tables concerning consumption and occurrence data.

3.5 User guidance

MCRA includes online documentation (<https://mcra.rivm.nl/mcra9/WebApp/manual/index.html>). This documentation consists of a user manual, a reference manual and a bibliography. The user manual provides information about the structure of MCRA and some practical examples including exercises.

3.5.1 User guidance for data providers

The reference manual provides information about the various modules that makes up MCRA. The description of the data format for each table can also be found here. It is also possible to download an empty dataset template (zipped csv or Excel) for each data group. In Appendix 1 the data structure for the tables which can be used for exposure assessments using TDS data are explained. The information for the data needed can also be found in the section 'Standard actions', which is part of the MCRA online reference manual.

Figure 1. Overview of the data sources needed for TDS-based long term dietary exposure and risk assessment.

3.5.2 User guidance for end users

The MCRA online documentation includes the section ‘Standard actions’, which is part of the reference manual.

This section describes the demonstrators in more detail (under construction). For each demonstrator discussed in chapter 3 further information regarding the purpose, settings and the tables used is provided (see Figure 2). In the coming months this documentation will be extended to explain the use of the demonstrator as well as providing a more detailed description of the settings and the tables used. The purpose of the demonstrator is to first show a user how to perform a TDS-based long term dietary exposure and secondly assist the user in organizing and using own data.

Also, the information provided in Appendix 2, 3, 4 and 5 will be included in the online documentation.

The screenshot shows the MCRA Documentation web interface. On the left is a sidebar with a search bar and navigation sections: 'USER GUIDE' (Introduction to MCRA, Examples), 'REFERENCE MANUAL' (Modules), and 'Standard actions'. The 'Standard actions' list includes: 'Chronic cumulative exposure assessment PA', 'Chronic cumulative exposure assessment PFAS', 'Demo acute cumulative risk assessment', 'Demo Human Monitoring Analysis bisphenols', 'TDS-based long term dietary exposure and risk assessment', 'Long-term dietary exposure and risk of nickel for the Belgian population', 'TDS-based long-term exposure and risk assessment of methylmercury for German children' (highlighted), 'Introduction', 'Standard action options', 'Standard action data', and 'EU acute cumulative exposure assessment (OP2) The Food Trail II'. The main content area displays the title 'TDS-based long-term exposure and risk assessment of methylmercury for German children' with a breadcrumb trail 'Standard actions > TDS-based long-term exposure and risk assessment of methylmercury for German children'. Below the title, it states 'This standard action is of type: RISKS'. A 'Note' box contains the text: 'This standard action was developed within the FNS-Cloud project (<https://www.fns-cloud.eu>). Related consumption data and example conversion scripts for uploading data will be made available in the FNS Cloud (state 11/2021: in progress)'. The 'Introduction' section follows, describing the probabilistic risk assessment of methylmercury exposure for German children, mentioning the Total Diet Study (TDS) data, stratification by region and production type, and the use of the Observed Individual Means model for exposure calculation. It also notes that the exposure is compared to the tolerable weekly intake (TWI) of 1.3 µg per kg body weight and day set by EFSA.

Figure 2. MCRA documentation: TDS-based long term dietary exposure and risk assessment of methylmercury for German children: one of the FNS-Cloud demonstrators.

4 Low-end user app demonstrator

4.1 Description and purpose of the tool

The purpose of Total Diet Studies is to measure the average amount of a wide range of substances in foods “as consumed”. The results provide a basis for national risk assessments and are therefore mainly partially published as part of opinions and statements. That means, the majority of the general public are either unaware of this data or they consider it hard to find or understand. However, policies driving transparency and open data are of growing interest, not only for explaining risk assessments but also regarding conducted large-scale studies, financed from public funds. Accordingly, there are various efforts to make TDS more open to the public, for instance the creation of study-own web pages and the presentation on social media and consumer-oriented fairs, as performed for the BfR MEAL study (<http://www.bfr-meal-studie.de>). Whereas these attempts are useful in raising awareness of TDS and some selected results; the presentation of the complete study results is an entirely different matter as it holds major challenges, such as

- Making complex datasets accessible for the lay public, i.e., the appropriate presentation of the data so as not to overstrain the users (e. g. in BfR MEAL study, around 300 substances were considered and around 60.000 different foods, aggregated to ~ 4.000 pools, analyzed)
- Making the data understandable, i.e., the insertion of explanation and assistance as non-professionals may not be able to understand and evaluate the presented information

Keeping in mind the particular challenges of the presentation of TDS data, a low-end user app is in development as an alternative to the publication of TDS datasets via Excel or public use file.

In terms of transparency and FAIR data, there have been a number of efforts to publish TDS data and to make them available even for the general public. This includes the publication of excel files via popular data repositories or public use files on institution-owned web pages. However, publishing TDS datasets requires either a very heavy workload or that leaving the data as only usable by professionals. Currently, there are no options to publish TDS data and make them understandable for the general public without a huge effort for the data owners. Therefore, the low-end user app has the purpose to give institutions the opportunity to communicate their TDS data in a simple way without a lot of workloads.

On the other hand, consumer interest in health, nutrition and transparency with regard to related studies and data is growing (Krebs, 2003). Accordingly, the presentation of the TDS data needs to align with people’s interest as well as with their background knowledge in the topic. Therefore, the second purpose of the app is to make TDS data accessible and understandable for the general public.

Summarising, the development of the app has two major purposes:

- (1) Support institutions publishing their TDS data and
- (2) Inform low-end users about contents of substances in foods.

4.2 User guidance

Although there will be several test rounds to test the functionality, technical implementation and understandability of the app, conceptual gaps between the lay users and what the app designers expect

these users to know might still be existent. To close these gaps, user assistances can help to guide users through the app. As these gaps differ between the defined user groups (data provider and end-users) in addition to the intentions to use the app and the type of use, two different user guides need to be provided, adapted to the respective user group.

User assistance for data providers should be developed in order to answer questions like why we should publish data via the app/ which data need to be provided/ how should the data be organized and coded. Assistance for end-users should however focus on the content and structure of the app and operating elements. Additionally, whereas the user assistance for data provider should provide clear instructions and be detailed and comprehensive, the end-users guide for an App should strive for being interesting, “make you want more”, assist the users if its needed and be “invisible” if not.

4.2.1 User guidance for data providers

The app is designed to be an option for the publication of all existing and future TDS. In order to develop a concept that fits more or less with all TDS datasets, the structure of the large-scale BfR MEAL study was used to provide a framework for the publication of other TDS results. Accordingly, datasets coming from the different institutions need to be organized and described in a distinctive way to fit the requirements of the system. This relates, among other things, such as the description of analyzed foods and substances, as existing classification systems like FoodEx2 (for foods) or SSD2 (for substances) are not applied by all TDS-conducting institutions. In addition, classification of substances in groups differ between TDSs. E. g. in BfR MEAL study, analyzed substances were classified into 9 groups (Bürgelt et al., 2016), in TDS Exposure project, 8 substance groups were proposed (Vin et al., 2014) and in the French TDS on infants, substances were classified into 19 groups (Hulin et al., 2014). Therefore, it is not possible to use pre-defined substance groups, those need to be defined individually by the data provider.

Accordingly, requirements on datasets (which data?) and data format (how should the datasets be prepared, including codes and translations) needs to be described. Information will be communicated to the data owners as part of a written user guide. Besides defining the requirements on the datasets and data format, the user manual covers a brief introduction to the application. The complete manual is attached to this report (see Appendix 6).

4.2.1.1 Introduction and general information for data provider

It can be assumed that some data owners already have some knowledge about the application. However, others might not know the app at all. Therefore, some basic information should be provided. This includes an introduction into the app, explaining the purpose, funding and development of the app. The concept and structure will be presented by means of some screens. Furthermore, it will be mentioned what kind of data can be uploaded, who is able to do it and who are the addressees of the app.

4.2.1.2 Requirements on data sets and data formats

The second part of the user guide deals with the requirements on the datasets and how they should be prepared to guarantee an unambiguous allocation of the information and the precise linking between the tables. This part should provide answers to the following questions:

- Which data are required?
- How should the data be organized?
- How should data be classified/coded (e. g. in accordance with FoodEx2)?
- What are the requirements with regard to text segments?

- How to transmit the data?

Related to the question “which data are required”, a distinction should be made between the minimum information needed to present TDS data in the app that, at the same time, can be provided by all institutions, and additional information to make the data more understandable which is not imperatively required. This relates to the organization of the app, consisting of a section presenting the content data and an additional section with further information regarding exposure assessments and the contribution of food groups to exposure. E. g., as content data are the outcome of TDS, these data is expected to be provided for all TDS. However, additional calculations (exposure assessments, contribution to exposure), might exist for several TDS but it cannot be assumed that these calculations can be provided for all of them. As one of the app’s purposes is to be an option to communicate TDS data without much effort, it should not be expected from the data owners to conduct further analysis, unless it already exists.

Accordingly, all data and information included in the app were revised and categorized:

Category 1: Data and information needed to fulfill basic purposes of the app (transparency, make TDS data available). These data and information are obligatory, without them, no publication via the low-end user app is possible. Classified as category 1 data and information are:

- Content data tables (coded TDS foods + groups, analyzed substances + groups, analytical limits, results and respective units)
- Translation tables (for foods, food groups, substances and substance groups)
- Short description of the study (name, acronym, country, institution and description)

Category 2: Data and information, which are crucial to fulfill the purpose of the app to make TDS data understandable for the users. Nevertheless, as these data and information are not necessarily part of TDS and therefore might not be available, these data and information are not imperatively required but highly recommended to be provided.

Classified as category 2 are:

- A general assessment (providing a short “easy-to-understand” statement whether toxicological reference values are reached regarding the population-based exposure assessments)
- Exposure assessment tables (substance, population group, production type and exposure – differentiated between mean and high intake, both lower bound and upper bound)
- Contribution of food groups to exposure (substance, population group, production type, food group and their contribution to dietary exposure – for both lower bound and upper bound).

For each table and parameter, the data provider’s guide defines the coding of the table and parameters and possible particularities (e.g., limitation of characters for text segments).

4.2.2 User assistance for end users

The intuitive handling and ease of understanding are seen as important features of apps (Schmitz et al., 2016). Accordingly, in the ideal case, apps do not need any user assistance (UA) at all. However, there might still be a gap between the expectation of the developers on user’s knowledge and their actual capabilities. In order to overcome possible difficulties of handling and use of the application, UA elements can be helpful (Ginon, 2012). UA generally includes all guided assistance elements helping users to navigate through the app, accomplish tasks and enhance user experience (Acar & Tekinerdogan, 2020).

4.2.2.1 User assistance formats

Overall, there are several opportunities to “train” or “assist” users. Generally, a differentiation can be made between User assistance/guidance elements embedded in the application and separated from the system (= external).

External UA are defined as help in a help interface such as in a web browser, video player or even in paper form, instead of help in the actual app interface itself (Yeh et al., 2011). Although the actual interface (of the app) and the help interface (user manual) are split, nowadays, user manuals can be linked in the application and therefore be provided as external automated user assistance online. Still, this kind of user assistance poses major usability problems: split-attention as using the UA means a disruption of the user’s flow of work, a separate effort and delayed practice as they need to switch between two interfaces (Acar & Tekinerdogan, 2020; Yeh et al., 2011). However, external UA also have advantages as they can be linked not only in the application but also on the websites of the participating institutions informing potential users about the app, its contents and its handling.

As an alternative, user assistant elements can be embedded (“in-app”) and therefore be opened in the application, leading to an enhanced user experience (Acar & Tekinerdogan, 2020) and ensuring a minimum of disturbance of the user’s flow of using the app. Users receive support in the actual interface (of the app) they are interacting with and don’t need to open another interface. This solves the major usability problems (split-attention and lack of support of practice) as contextual help allows hands-on practice and exploration at the same time (Yeh et al., 2011).

Contextual help can be realized in different ways, e.g., as tooltips, tool clips, initial guidance and stencil-based tutorials. Of all options, tooltips (pop-up windows) are the most common form for contextual help (Yeh et al., 2011) and can be provided as *inline help* buttons (small, static icon with a question mark inside). They can be used to support users on known trouble spots. Usually, *inline help* buttons are UA elements revealing app-specific help documentation when clicked. They can launch a popover message or even a whole guide. The respective text is not directly embedded in the interface, so it does not distract people. This makes it great for features that the majority of the users a) already know how to use, or b) intuitively know how to use. While general help buttons are usually placed on the top on the screen, so-called *inline help* buttons or question marks are placed at specific sections and are therefore related to just this section. Besides being specific, *inline help* buttons are defined as being contextual, and timely and appear when a user is most likely to interact.

4.2.2.2 Criteria for selecting the guidance format

Various aspects were considered for the selection of the form of user guidance appropriate for the low-end user app:

a. Advantages and disadvantages of the guidance formats

In general, both guidance formats (external and contextual) have specific advantages, as described in 4.2.2.1. Overall, external guidance formats mean a disruption of user’s flow of work and a switch between interfaces but are still interesting in matter of explaining the app’s purposes and major functions in a comprehensive way. Additionally, they can be linked on websites of participating institutions and therefore make aware of the existence of the app. Contextual help on the other way represent the possibility to assist users without interrupting their workflow, providing information where and if needed.

b. Development status of the app

Currently, the implementation of the 1st version is in progress. There are still several feedback/test rounds planned, likely leading to improvements and changes of the user interface. This leads to an exclusion of inflexible user guidance formats, e.g., explainer videos, as a replacement of screens within the video is technically not feasible. Explainer and tutorial videos could be considered for the final version of the app but

not at the current developmental state. Same applies to printed user manuals (or pdfs), although a replacement of screens would mean less effort. Changes of the user interface also affect contextual help elements as after every change it must be reviewed if additional elements or some adjustments of the belonging text are necessary. However, the related workload can be considered as not as big as the production of a new explainer or tutorial video.

c. Necessity of user guidance

Overall, the app is supposed to be self-explaining. The app's purpose is mainly to be informative. No user-based calculation (e. g. individual calculation of exposure towards substances) are included. It is quite likely that most of the users don't even need a user guidance. Still, users need to search for substances and foods as well as make selections which might need instructions. Additionally, user guidance can explain the structure of the app and therefore prevent a time-consuming self-exploration of the app by the user.

Thus, provided user guidance need to be developed in order to adjust to potential differences of user's abilities to use applications and their topic-related background knowledge. Accordingly, there will be users with no need in further instructions as well as users reliant on a little support and users reliant on information that is more comprehensive. Comprehensive explainer or tutorial videos do not meet these requirements, as it is already pre-decided which information will be provided to the user. User manuals as pdf might have the option to go directly to a specific section. However, this implies that users know what to look for. Contextual help on the other hand appears where it is needed and refers only to the specific topic/operating element. Additionally, the use of the information is optional; it may or may not be retrieved by the users, considering the differences between user's knowledge and interest.

d. Likely use of the app (situation and used electronical device)

In addition, it needs to be considered in which situation the help might be needed and what device is used. If users are at home with time to explore the app, they have time to read/watch comprehensive user manuals. On contrary if users are outside, e. g. during grocery shopping, there is no time to read a complete manual or watch a video. In such situations the principle "as much as necessary, as little as possible" is certainly applicable. Additionally, outside it is most likely that the app is used on small screens (smartphone) which make an adjustment of the user guidance to small screens necessary. This excludes videos and is also difficult for written user manuals.

Taking all aspects into account it was decided at the current developmental state of the app to provide contextual help in the form of *inline help* buttons (tooltips). These *inline help* buttons will be placed wherever necessary, explaining the structure and choices wherever needed. When users press the *inline help* button a popover will be displayed with an explanation specific for the respective section.

See Appendix 6 and 7 for the User manuals.

5 Conclusions

In Task 4.3 of the FNS-Cloud five demonstrators are developed. Four demonstrators are intended to be used by high-end users, e.g., risk assessors and researchers. Using TDS or monitoring data for higher-tier more complex risk assessments. Specifically, the latter approach will use the probabilistic assessment with the Monte Carlo Risk Assessment (MCRA) tool.

The fifth demonstrator is intended for use by Low-end users (e. g. consumers, non-TDS-experts). By using the mobile app, low-end users will be able to inform themselves about concentration data in foods (based on TDS) within decision making processes in their daily life, e.g., in the supermarket when purchasing foods.

The next step in this project will be the discussion about how these resources can be used in the future. The outcome of this discussion will be discussed in Deliverable 5.9. This deliverable is planned at the end of the FNS-Cloud project.

References

- Acar, M., Tekinerdogan, B. (2020): Analyzing the impact of automated user assistance systems: A systematic review. In: *arXiv preprint arXiv:2003.05782*, 1-22. <https://arxiv.org/ftp/arxiv/papers/2003/2003.05782.pdf>
- Bürgelt, M., Sarvan, I., Greiner, M., Lindtner, O. (2016): Was im Essen steckt - die MEAL-Studie des Bundesinstituts für Risikobewertung. In: *UMID* 2, 38-43. <https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/publikationen/umid-022016>.
- Ginon, B. (2012): Towards a generic model for user assistance. In: *International Conference on User Modeling, Adaption, and Personalization*, 356-360. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg. https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007%2F978-3-642-31454-4_35
- Hulin, M., Bemrah, N., Nougadere, A., Volatier, J.L., Sirot, V., Leblanc, J.C. (2014): Assessment of infant exposure to food chemicals: the French Total Diet Study design. In: *Food Additives & Contaminants: Part A* 31:7, 1226-1239. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/24827474/>
- Klaveren, J.D. van (2019), J.W. Kruisselbrink, W.J. de Boer, G. van Donkersgoed, J.D. te Biesebeek, M. Sam, H. van der Voet, Cumulative dietary exposure assessment of pesticides that have acute effects on the nervous system using MCRA software. EFSA supporting publication 2019:EN-1708. 95 pp. <https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2019.EN-1708>
- Krebs (2003): Giving the public the full food facts. In: *Financial times*, 13 November, p.22
- Schmitz, Ch., Bartsch, S., Meyer, A. (2016): Mobile app usage and its implications for service management – empirical findings from German public transport. In: *Procedia – Social and Behavioral Science* 224, 230-237. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1877042816305936>
- Vin, K., Papadopoulos, A., Cubadda, F., Aureli, F., Basegmez, H.I.O, D’Amato, M., De Coster, S., D’Evoli, L., Lopez Esteban, M.T., Jurkovic, M., Lucarini, M., Ozer, H., Fernandez San Juan, P.M., Sioen, I., Sokolic, D., Turrini, A., Sirot, V. (2014): TDS exposure project: Relevance of the Total Diet Study approach for different groups of substances. In: *Food and Chemical Toxicology* 73, 21-34. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/25106751/>
- Yeh, T., Chang, T.-H., Xie, B., Walsh, G., Watkins, I., Wongsuphasawat, K., Huang, M., Davis, L. S., Bederson, B (2011): Creating contextual help for GUIs using screenshots. In: *Proc. of UIST 2011*.

Abbreviations

BfR	Bundesinstitut für Risikobewertung
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
MCRA	Monte Carlo Risk Assessment
RIVM	Rijksinstituut voor Volksgezondheid en Milieu
TDS	Total Diet Study
UA	User assistance
UGent	University of Ghent, Belgium
WHO	World Health Organization
WUR	Wageningen University and Research

Appendix 1 - Training materials TDS-exposure harmonised – data organisation

Harmonized (TDS) exposure and risk assessment

Exposure and risk

Distribution of the individual exposures calculated using the OIM model.

Distribution of the hazard quotients of the individuals using the OIM model.

MCRA Harmonised TDS demonstrator

Included TDSs:

- NL TDS on mycotoxins for children, 2016
- DE VELs consumption survey 2001-2002 combined with artificial TDS concentration data following the MEALS format
- BE consumption survey 2014-2015 combined with TDS concentration data on nickel

Options:

- NL Mycotoxins (DON)
- DE MeHg
- BE Ni

Datasets and data organisation

1. Consumptions - format

MCRA | Data organization, February, 2022

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1. Consumptions - example

MCRA | Data organization, February, 2022

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2. Concentrations - format

Table ConcentrationsSSD

Field Name	Data Type
labSampCode	Short Text
labSubSampCode	Short Text
sampCountry	Short Text
prodCode	Short Text
sampY	Number
sampM	Number
sampD	Number
analysisY	Number
analysisM	Number
analysisD	Number
paramCode	Short Text
resUnit	Short Text
resLOD	Number
resLOQ	Number
resVal	Number
resType	Short Text

Table TDSFoodSampleCompositions

Field Name	Data Type
idTDSFood	Short Text
idFood	Short Text
PooledAmount	Number

The TDS food sample compositions table contains the descriptions of the TDS samples and specifications of the foods (with amounts) included in the TDS samples.

Concentrations data are analytical measurements of chemical substances occurring in food samples.

2. Concentrations - example

Table Concentrations SSD

labSampCode	prodCode	sampCountry	sampY	sampM	sampD	analysisY	analysisM	analysisD	paramCode	resUnit	resLOD	resVAL	resType
100	MENG_ROOM.24-36	NL	2018	1	12	2018	1	12	RF-00000213-TOX	G050A	1.2		LOD
100	MENG_ROOM.24-36	NL	2018	1	12	2018	1	12	RF-00000435-TOX	G050A	0.1	0.0002	VAL
101	MENG_RUND.COMBI	NL	2018	1	12	2018	1	12	RF-00000435-TOX	G050A	0.1	0.2	VAL
102	MENG_SAPP1.COMBI	NL	2018	1	12	2018	1	12	RF-00000157-TOX	G050A	5		LOD
102	MENG_SAPP1.COMBI	NL	2018	1	12	2018	1	12	RF-00000191-TOX	G050A	1		LOD
102	MENG_SAPP1.COMBI	NL	2018	1	12	2018	1	12	RF-00000192-TOX	G050A	0.3		LOD

Table TDSFoodSampleCompositions

idTDSFood	idFood	PooledAmount
MENG_ROOM.24-36	A02ML	17
MENG_ROOM.24-36	A02QA	83
MENG_RUND.COMBI	A049S	100
MENG_SAPP1.COMBI	A039M	100
MENG_SAPP2.24-36	A03EA	51

3. Catalogues - substances

Table Substances (format)

Field Name	Data Type
IdSubstance	Short Text
SubstanceName	Short Text
Description	Short Text
ConcentrationUnit	Short Text
CramerClass	Number
MolecularMass	Number

In the substances table, the substance entities and other relevant substance properties that are relevant for the assessment at hand should be defined.

Table Substances (example)

IdSubstance	Name
RF-00002850-PAR	Total Deoxynivalenol
RF-00001337-PAR	Sum of Fumonisin B1 + B2
RF-00000440-TOX	Zearalenone and derivatives
RF-00000435-TOX	Aflatoxin (sum of B1, B2, G1, G2)

3. Catalogues - Foods

Table Foods (format)

Field Name	Data Type	
IdFood	Text	required, size 50
Name	Text	required, size 100

Table Foods (example)

A026F	Beerwurst
A00QG	Beetroots
A00AJ	Beignets
A01DT	Berries and small fruits
MENG.CRAC.12-18	beschuit, knackebrood
A01FE	Bilberries (generic)
A00AE	Biscuit with inclusions, filling or coating
A009V	Biscuits
MENG.KOEK.24-36	Biscuits
A00AB	Biscuits, oat meal
A03RA	Biscuits, rusks and cookies for child
A009X	Biscuits, sweet, plain
A00AA	Biscuits, sweet, wheat wholemeal
A034G	Bitter chocolate

The foods table is the main table of the food definitions. Includes all food codes present in Consumptions, ConcentrationsSSD, TDSFoodSampleComposition, FoodCompositions, ReadAcrossFoodTranslations, FoodHierarchy

3. Catalogues – Effects

Table Effects (format)

Field Name	Data Type
idEffect	Short Text
Name	Short Text
Description	Short Text

Effects are biological or toxicological consequences for human health, that may result from chemical exposure and are the focus of hazard or risk assessment.

Table Effects (example)

idEffect	Name	Description
Liver toxicity	Liver toxicity	Liver toxicity
Reduction Leukocyte count	Reduction Leukocyte count	Reduction Leukocyte count
Weight	Weight gain reduction	Weight gain reduction

3. Catalogues – HazardCharacterisations

Table HazardCharacterisations (format)

Field Name	Data Type
idHazardCharacterisation	Short Text
idEffect	Short Text
idSubstance	Short Text
idPopulationType	Short Text
TargetLevel	Short Text
ExposureType	Short Text
ExposureRoute	Short Text
TargetOrgan	Short Text
IsCriticalEffect	Yes/No
HazardCharacterisationType	Short Text
Qualifier	Short Text
HazardCharacterisationValue	Number
DoseUnit	Short Text
idPoD	Short Text
CombinedAssessmentFactor	Number
Author	Short Text
Title	Short Text
PublicationYear	Number
URL	Short Text
Remark	Short Text

Hazard characterisations are specified for combinations of hazard characterisation type, effect, substance, population type, target level, and exposure route (for external) or target organ (for internal).

Table HazardCharacterisations (example)

idHazardCharacterisation	idEffect	idSubstance	idPopulationType	TargetLevel	ExposureType	ExposureRoute	TargetOrgan	IsCriticalEff	HazardChar	Qualif	Hazarc	DoseUnit
Reduction Leukocyte count	Reduction Leukocyte	RF-00001320-TOX	Consumers	External	Chronic	Dietary		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TDI	=		0.02 ug/kg bw/day
Liver toxicity	Liver toxicity	RF-00001337-PAR	Consumers	External	Chronic	Dietary		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TDI	=		1 ug/kg bw/day
WeightLoss	Weight	RF-00002850-PAR	Consumers	External	Chronic	Dietary		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TDI	=		1 ug/kg bw/day

3. Catalogues - FoodCompositions (optional)

Table FoodCompositions (format)

Field Name	Data Type
idFromFood	Short Text
idToFood	Short Text
Proportion	Number
idPopulation	Short Text

Recipe data to specify the ingredients of foods. Food recipes can be used to describe the ingredients of a composite food (e.g., of apple pie), or to specify the amount of a primary ingredient needed to obtain 100g of the food (e.g., grapes to raisins)..

Table Foodtranslations (example)

idFromFood	idToFood	Proportion
A005K	MENG.BROO.24-36	0.4
A005K	MENG.BROO.24-36	33.2
A005K	MENG.BROO.24-36	67
A006B	MENG.BROO.24-36	12.8
A006Q	MENG.BROO.24-36	20
A007A	MENG.BROO.24-36	20

In case the coding used in the Consumption data is the same as the coding used in the Occurrence data you may not need this table.

3. Catalogues - ReadAcrossFoodTranslations (optional)

Table ReadAcrossFoodTranslations (format)

Field Name	Data Type
idFromFood	Short Text
idToFood	Short Text

Table ReadAcrossFoodTranslations (example)

idFromFood	idToFood
A011M	MENG.AARD.24-36
A011N	MENG.AARD.24-36
A011Q	MENG.AARD.24-36
A0BYV	MENG.AARD.24-36
A0BYX	MENG.AARD.24-36
A16FM	MENG.AARD.24-36
A01DJ	MENG.APPE.24-36
A01MC	MENG.APPE.24-36
A01PF	MENG.APPE.24-36
A01PJ	MENG.APPM.24-36
A01LC	MENG.BANA.COMB
A00KY	MENG.BLAD.24-36
A00KZ	MENG.BLAD.24-36

Food extrapolations (or read-across food translations) can be used to specify whether data (e.g. occurrence data) on a food for which this is missing (a data poor food) may be extrapolated from another food for which data is available (read-across food).

3. Catalogues – FoodHierarchy (optional)

Table FoodHierarchy (format)

Field Name	Data Type
idFood	Short Text
idParent	Number

Food items are commonly categorised in hierarchies, e.g. oranges and mandarins are citrus fruits.

Table FoodHierarchy (example)

idFood	idParent	
MENG.BROD.12-18		1
MENG.BROD.18-24		1
MENG.BROD.24-36		1
MENG.CRAC.12-18		1
MENG.CRAC.18-24		1
MENG.CRAC.26-36		1
MENG.ONTB.12-18		1
MENG.ONTB.18-24		1
MENG.ONTB.24-36		1
MENG.PAST.12-18		1
MENG.PAST.18-24		1
MENG.PAST.24-36		1
MENG.RUST.12-18		1
MENG.RUST.18-24		1
MENG.RUST.24-36		1
MENG.KOEK.12-18		3
MENG.KOEK.18-24		3

idParent 1 = Cereals and cereal based products. This code is present in the Foods table.

3. Catalogues –IndividualProperties (optional)

Table individualProperties (format)

Field Name	Data Type
idFood	Short Text
idParent	Number

This table is used to describe the properties used in the Populations or PopulationIndividualPropertyValues table characterising the population (table Populations) and/or the properties used in the Individuals table characterising an individual.

Table individualProperties (example)

idIndividual	Name	PropertyLev	Description	Type
Age		Individual		NonNegative
Breastfeeding		Individual		boolean
Country		Individual		Location
Date		IndividualDay		DateTime
Gender		Individual		Gender
Height		Individual		NonNegative
Month		IndividualDay		Month
Region		Individual		Categorical

3. Catalogues – Populations (optional)

Table Populations (format)

Field Name	Data Type
IdPopulation	Short Text
Name	Short Text
Description	Short Text
Country	Short Text
StartDate	Short Text
EndDate	Short Text
AgeMin	Short Text
AgeMax	Short Text
Region	Short Text
MonthMin	Short Text
MonthMax	Short Text

Populations identify human groups in e.g. dietary, nondietary and human monitoring surveys.

Table Populations (example)

IdPopulation	Name	Description	Country	StartDate	EndDate	AgeMin	AgeMax	Region	MonthMin	MonthMax
DE-Children-2001-2002	German children 2001/2002	German child	DE	2001-01-01	2002-12-31	0.5	6			
DE-Children-2001-2002-Conventional-Consumers	German children 2001/2002 conventional	German child	DE							
DE-Children-2001-2002-East	German children 2001/2002 region East	German child	DE	2001-01-01	2002-12-31	0.5	6	East		
DE-Children-2001-2002-East-Summer	German children 2001/2002 region East summer season	German child	DE	2001-03-01	2002-12-31	0.5	6	East	4	9
DE-Children-2001-2002-East-Winter	German children 2001/2002 region East winter season	German child	DE	2001-01-01	2002-12-31	0.5	6	East	10	3

3. Catalogues – PopulationPropertyValues (optional)

Table PopulationPropertyValues (format)

Field Name	Data Type
IdPopulation	Short Text
IdIndividualProperty	Short Text
Value	Short Text
MinValue	Short Text
MaxValue	Short Text

This table describes population individual properties, such as Age, Gender, Period, Region or Breastfeeding. Population individual property value are used to restrict the population to e.g. a range of ages, a gender, a certain time period, a geographical location or women giving breast feeding.

Table PopulationPropertyValues (example)

IdPopulation	IdIndividual	Value	MinValue	MaxValue
DE-Children-2001-2002-East	Region	East		
DE-Children-2001-2002-East-Summer	Region	East		
DE-Children-2001-2002-East-Summer	Month		4	9
DE-Children-2001-2002-East-Winter	Region	East		
DE-Children-2001-2002-East-Winter	Month		10	3
DE-Children-2001-2002-North	Region	North		
DE-Children-2001-2002-North-Summer	Region	North		
DE-Children-2001-2002-North-Summer	Month		4	9
DE-Children-2001-2002-North-Winter	Region	North		
DE-Children-2001-2002-North-Winter	Month		10	3
DE-Children-2001-2002-South	Region	South		
DE-Children-2001-2002-South-Summer	Region	South		

More information

- see MCRA documentation for data formats and much more

The screenshot shows the MCRA documentation interface. On the left is a navigation menu with categories like 'MCRA Documentation', 'MCRA Overview', 'Modules', 'Consumption modules', 'Consumption data formats', 'Food codes', 'High value consumption', 'Diagnosis modules', 'Exposure modules', 'Assessment modules', 'Prevalence modules', 'Survey modules', 'Risk modules', and 'Biomarker features'. The main content area is titled 'Consumptions data formats' and includes a description of consumption data, a section for 'Food consumption surveys' with a table of table definitions, and a 'Download empty dataset template' button.

Consumptions data formats

Consumption data is often collected in 24-hour dietary recall studies and contains the food consumptions and consumption amounts for a number of individuals over a number of days. For each of the individuals, the bodyweight should be specified, and optionally also age, sex, and other properties may be recorded. If applicable, sampling weight may also be specified that can be used to correct the sample of individuals in the survey to a more representative sample of the targeted population. The consumption amounts are usually expressed in grams, but may also be expressed in alternative units of grams, cups, or spoons. Optionally, the uncertainty of food consumption quantities can be specified, see [Sørensen et al. \(2013\)](#).

Consumption surveys are described using three tables: FoodSurveys, Individuals, and Consumptions. Individuals are linked to food surveys using the survey code (FoodSurvey), and consumptions are linked to individuals using the individual codes (Individual). The food codes used to identify the consumed foods should match with the codes provided by the foods entity definitions.

Download empty dataset template: [Download CSV](#) [Download](#)

Food consumption surveys

The records of the food consumption surveys table contains the title, names, descriptions, and other relevant metadata of consumption surveys.

Table alias: FoodConsumptionSurveys, ConsumptionSurveys, FoodSurveys, Surveys.

Table 28: Table definition for Food consumption surveys				
Name	Type	Description	Alias	Required
FoodSurvey	AlphaNumeric(255)	Unique identification code of the food consumption survey	FoodSurvey, FoodSurveySurvey, FoodSurveySurvey, FoodSurveyCode, FoodSurveyCodeID	No
Name	AlphaNumeric(255)	The name of the food consumption survey	Name, SurveyName	No

MCRA | Data organization, February, 2022

Appendix 2 - Training materials TDS-exposure harmonised – guidance end users

Slide 1 features a vibrant image of various fruits and vegetables on the left. On the right, a blue background contains the following text and logos:

- National Institute for Public Health and the Environment
Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sport
- WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY & RESEARCH
- TDS harmonized
 - standard action
 - upload data
 - full action

Slide 2 displays the MCRA interface with logos for the National Institute for Public Health and the Environment and Wageningen University & Research at the top.

MCRA

- > mcra.rivm.nl
- > MCRA 9

Welcome to MCRA
Please select the version of MCRA that you wish to use.

MCRA 9 	
---	---

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Opening page with short explanation

Welcome to MCRA 9
Chemical exposure, hazard and risk assessment

On a daily basis, people are exposed to multiple chemicals via food intake, inhalation and dermal contact. The risk to human health resulting from this exposure depends on the effects of the different chemicals in the mixture and how they combine. MCRA stands for **Monte Carlo Risk Assessment**. It is a web-based platform containing various models that users can use to assess these health risks for specific populations in various scenarios.

In MCRA, more than 50 modules are available to address all major areas of risk assessment, including hazard identification, hazard characterisation, exposure assessment and risk assessment. MCRA contains models following the guidelines of the European Commission and the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), and also includes novel scientific models that could improve or refine future risk assessment.

MCRA 9 was developed in EU project EuroMix (2015-2019) and in a partnership between EFSA, RIVM and WUR (2018-2020) to assess risks from combined exposure to multiple chemicals from multiple routes of exposure using deterministic or probabilistic methods.

[MCRA documentation](#) [Publications and reports using MCRA](#)

MCRA account
MCRA is available for registered stakeholders. An account can be requested by filling in the registration form.

[Register for an account](#)

Do you already have an account? [Log in here](#)

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Login

Log in

Login

[Forgot password](#) [Create an account](#)

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4

Create workspace

- > Select workspaces

Using MCRA

You can specify your models, such as a dietary exposure assessment, within **actions** that are organised in **workspaces**. Each action is of a **module type** and contains selected data and settings. After specifying data and settings, the modelling task can be started. The output report contains concise sections of main results and detailed drilldown information.

The data used in the actions is organised in the **data repository**. Users have their own private data repository for uploading data. In addition, shared repository folders are available used for sharing data among user groups.

For more information on using MCRA consult the [documentation pages](#).

Contact: MCRA Support, National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM).

MCRA is developed by Wageningen University & Research, Biometris for RIVM and EFSA (2007 - 2022)

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Create workspace

- > Create workspace by clicking
- > Give the workspace a name and click on 'OK'

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Create standard action (1)

- > Create a standard action by clicking
- > Select create standard action

7

Create standard action (2)

- > Select TDS-based long term dietary exposure and risk assessment

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8

Specify name/description and create

- > Specify a name
- > Press **create**

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9

Inspect settings

- Select TDS Mycotoxins NL children 2016
- Press **Save Changes**

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Press run

- > Run the action by clicking

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Wait for completion and open the report

- > Wait until the job has finished →
- > Open output report by clicking the link

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Browse through the report

- › Browse through the report

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Exercise E1

- › Report the exposure at the 50- and 95-percentile.
- › Which foods are contributing most to the dietary exposure at Level 0?
- › Which 3 foods are contributing most to the dietary exposure at Level 1?

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Exposure at p50- and p95

Percentiles hazard index.

Percentage	Exposure (µg/kg/day)	Hazard Index
50.00	0.2199	0.2199
95.00	0.8148	0.8148

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Foods contributing the most at level 0

Food	Contribution (%)
Cereals and cereal based products	71.5
Confectionery	26.2
Porridge	1.8

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Foods contributing the most at level 1

Food	Contribution (%)
Pasta	43
Bread	21.8
Biscuits	17.6

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Upload own data

- > Occurrence data for Ochratoxin A are available for the Dutch TDS
- > Upload own Hazard characterisations data and Effects data containing information for OTA
- > Click on

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Upload own data (1)

- > Click on Data
- > Folder Data / TrainingTDS-WHOxx is your own personal folder: you can upload here own data.
- > The other folders are shared folders: you are granted to use these data, but you can not download the datafiles.
- > Click on TrainingTDS-WHOxx

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Upload own data (2)

- > Upload your own data
 - HazardCharacterisationsExtra.xlsx
- > Make sure you are on your own MCRA folder (**Data/TrainingTDS-WHO..**)
- > Click on
- > Select Upload new file(s)
- > Search for data on your computer
- > Upload the new file(s)

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Clone to full action (1)

- > Click on the action TDS-based long ter..

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Clone to full action (2)

- > Click ⋮
- > Select Clone to full action

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Change Hazard characterisations (1)

> Select 'Hazard characterisations'

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Change Hazard characterisations (2)

> Select the pencil and select Browse

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Browse to the uploaded own data (1)

- > You have no right to store own data in the Standard Actions data share, therefore you have to browse to your personal data share
- > Click Top level Data
- > Click your personal data share (labeled with your user name)
- > Click the file that was uploaded before
- > Click Select

Training Mixture Risk Assessment | March/April 2022

Browse to the uploaded own data (2)

- > At the bottom of your screen you can see this file contains data on Effects and Hazard characterisations
- > Click Toggle all
- > Click Select

Training Mixture Risk Assessment | March/April 2022

Make selections for Ochratoxin A (1)

- > We want to select the hazard characterisation for Ochratoxin A (paramCode=RF-00000148-TOX)
- > Click on the pencil behind Hazard characterisations: selected 1 of 3

MCRA 9
Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment

TDS-based long term dietary exposure and risk assessment (1)

Summary

- Populations ✓
- Effects ✓
- Foods ✓
- Substances ✓
- Risks ✓
 - Concentration models ✓
 - Consumptions by modelled food ✓
 - Dietary exposures ✓
 - Food conversions ✓
 - Modelled foods ✓
 - Concentrations ✓
 - Consumptions ✓
 - Food extrapolations ✓
 - Food recipes ✓
 - Hazard characterisations ✓

Risks / Hazard characterisations

Hazard characterisations

Use data Compute

Hazard characterisations data source

#HazardCharacterisationsExtra.xlsx

Inputs

Substances (1 selected) ✓

Effects (1 selected) ✓

Populations ✓

Points of departure (optional)

Hazard characterisations data selection

Hazard characterisations: selected 1 of 3 (no filter) | (set filter)

Training Mixture Risk Assessment | March/April 2022

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Make selections for Ochratoxin A (2)

- > We want to select the hazard characterisation for Ochratoxin A (paramCode=RF-00000148-TOX)
- > Click Save

Hazard characterisations selection

Show selected

1 entries selected

<input type="checkbox"/>	Code	Name
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWI-RF-00000148-TOX-EFSA-2020	
<input type="checkbox"/>	TDI-RF-00002850-PAR-EFSA-2017	
<input type="checkbox"/>	TWI-RF-00000169-CHE-EFSA-2012	

Items per page: 15 1 - 3 of 3

Cancel Save

Training Mixture Risk Assessment | March/April 2022

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Make selections for Ochratoxin A (3)

- We want to change the effect to the effect of Ochratoxin A
- Select Effects

Training Mixture Risk Assessment | March/April 2022

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Make selections for Ochratoxin A (4)

- Click on the pencil behind Effects selection
- Select Kidney-disease and Click on Save

Training Mixture Risk Assessment | March/April 2022

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Make selections for Ochratoxin A (5)

- > We want to change the substance to Ochratoxin A
- > Select Substances

Training Mixture Risk Assessment | March/April 2022

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Make selections for Ochratoxin A (6)

- > Click on the pencil behind Substances selection
- > Select RF-00000148-TOX Ochratoxin A
- > Click on Save

Training Mixture Risk Assessment | March/April 2022

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Press run

- Run the action by clicking

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Rename the output

- Rename the output by clicking on
- Rename to e.g. TDS mycotoxins NL Children 2016-OTA

Output	Status	Message	Date	Running time
<input type="checkbox"/> TDS Mycotoxins NL Children 2016 (1)	Ran to completion		15-04-2022 11:55	00:00:03

Training Mixture Risk Assessment | March/April 2022 34

Results

- > View the results by clicking on the name of the output

Results				
Output	Status	Message	Date	Running time
<input type="checkbox"/> TDS Mycotoxins NL Children 2016 -OTA	Run to completion		15-04-2022 11:55	00:00:03

Appendix 3 - Training materials TDS-exposure German children to methylmercury

GERMAN FEDERAL INSTITUTE
FOR RISK ASSESSMENT

Bundesinstitut für Risikobewertung

Standard Action 'TDS-based long-term exposure and risk assessment of methylmercury for German children'

Outline

- (1) Concept of MCRA Standard Actions
- (2) Creating a new Standard Action
- (3) Structure & setting options of the Standard Action 'TDS-based long-term exposure and risk assessment of methylmercury for German children'
- (4) Exercises
- (5) Solutions

MCRA standard Action MeHg

page 2

Concept > Creating a SA > Structure & Settings > Exercises > Solutions

(1) MCRA: the concept of Standard Actions

- For use for exposure/risk assessment trainings
- simplified user surface with pre-defined selection options
- Pre-defined example datasets
- Allows quick and easy assessments
- No/little prior knowledge in exposure assessment required
- Avoids complex data preparation and settings for assessments

MCRA standard Action MeHg

page 3

Concept > Creating a SA > Structure & Settings > Exercises > Solutions

(2) Creating a new Standard Action

1. Log in to MCRA 9.1

- Visit: <https://mcra.rivm.nl/Mcra91/WebApp/#/>
- Click on 'log in here' and insert your Username and Password

MCRA standard Action MeHg

page 4

2. Create a Workspace

Welcome to MCRA 9.1
Chemical exposure, hazard and risk assessment

MCRA can perform 51 **action types**, for example dietary exposure assessment, dose response modelling, hazard characterisation and risk assessment. Actions are structured in a **network of modules**.

Use **workspaces** to create or clone **actions** of a specific action type, by providing data and settings. Actions may need subactions of other action types. You can run the main action or any of its subactions. Actions can be fully customised by the MCRA user, but for simplified use a series of **standard actions** is being developed.

After running an action or subaction, **results** are available. Results are in the form of screen reports, print reports and/or tables for download, and may also include output data that are useful as input for other actions.

Data are organised in a data repository, which includes shared folders from other users and user groups.

Start by clicking **Workspaces** or **Data**

Workspaces **Data**

MCRA documentation **Publications and reports using MCRA**

Contact: MCRA Support, National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM).
MCRA is developed by Wageningen University & Research, Biometris for RIVM and EFSA (2007 - 2021)

2. Create a Workspace

1. Create a new workspace by clicking the green plus ('+') on the bottom right of the page
2. Give the new workspace a name (free choice) and confirm with 'OK'

Create new workspace

Create a new workspace, please provide a descriptive name:

Test_MeHg

OK Cancel

Concept > Creating a SA > Structure & Settings > Exercises > Solutions

3. Create a new standard action

1. Create a standard action by clicking the green plus ('+') on the bottom right of the page
2. Select 'Create standard action'. A new window will open.

MCRA standard Action MeHg

page 7 BfR

Concept > Creating a SA > Structure & Settings > Exercises > Solutions

4. Create a new standard action

- Select standard action 'TDS-based long-term exposure and risk assessment of methylmercury for German children'

MCRA standard Action MeHg

page 8 BfR

Concept > Creating a SA > Structure & Settings > Exercises > Solutions

4. Create a new standard action

1. Give name and/or tags and description of the standard action
 - The name is provided but can be changed
 - Tags and description serve for additional documentation. These are optional.
2. Press 'create'

MCRA standard Action MeHg

page 9

Concept > Creating a SA > Structure & Settings > Exercises > Solutions

3. Open Standard Action

- Next time you open MCTA the Standard Action will be included in the Workspaces

Welcome to MCRA 9.1
Chemical exposure, hazard and risk assessment

MCRA can perform 51 **action types**, for example dietary exposure assessment, dose response modelling, hazard characterisation and risk assessment. Actions are structured in a **network of modules**.

Use **workspaces** to create or clone **actions** of a specific action type, by providing data and settings. Actions may need subactions of other action types. You can run the main action or any of its subactions. Actions can be fully customised by the MCRA user, but for simplified use a series of **standard actions** is being developed.

After running an action or subaction, **results** are available. Results are in the form of screen reports, print reports and/or tables for download, and may also include output data that are useful as input for other actions.

Data are organised in a data repository, which includes shared folders from other users and user groups.

Start by clicking **Workspaces** or **Data**

Workspaces | **Data**

MCRA documentation | Publications and reports using MCRA

Contact: MCRA Support, National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM).
MCRA is developed by Wageningen University & Research, Biomatrix for RIVM and EFSA (2007 - 2021)

Name	Created	Last modified
Dietary TDG Action	26-11-2019 14:11	26-11-2019 15:02
StandardAction_MeHg_V2	01-12-2021 19:38	07-01-2022 15:38
StandardAction_UHMMe_V1	22-10-2021 14:41	22-10-2021 16:38
TDG-Exposure 2014-2015	18-10-2019 14:48	04-03-2020 14:41
Test_MeHg_V1	04-03-2020 12:54	14-03-2020 16:11
Test_MeHg_V10	27-04-2021 10:29	22-10-2021 16:11
Test_MeHg_V12	12-11-2021 10:36	09-12-2021 15:42
Test_MeHg_V2	18-09-2020 16:12	18-03-2020 15:05
Test_MeHg_V3	03-04-2020 15:42	03-04-2020 15:05
Test_MeHg_V6	27-01-2021 16:42	27-01-2021 15:44
Test_MeHg_V7	14-02-2021 08:48	04-03-2021 10:04
Test Module v3	11-03-2021 14:43	01-04-2021 13:30

MCRA standard Action MeHg

page 10

(3) Structure & setting options

- The documentation gives a brief overview, what can be assessed with this standard action and how to understand the selection options.

Introduction to the setting options

Concept > Creating a SA > Structure & Settings > Exercises > Solutions

Introduction to the setting options

page 13

Concept > Creating a SA > Structure & Settings > Exercises > Solutions

Exercises

- Please see the handout for exercises
- Conduct all of the exercises on your own and note the answers to the posed questions
- Your are free to ask any question in case you cannot proceed
- Note that the here presented occurrence data on methylmercury are artificially created to depict differences in regional, seasonal and production type stratifications!*

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Concept > Creating a SA > Structure & Settings > Exercises > Solutions

Solutions

1) Calculate overall exposure (conventional production, consumers only, LB)

- (1) What is the mean and median exposure?
- (2) What is the HI at P50 and what does it mean?
- (3) What is the main contributing main food group?
- (4) What are the three main contributors at food level?

The tolerable weekly intake (TWI) for methylmercury expressed as mercury is 1.3 µg/kg BW (<https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2012.2985>), corresponding to a tolerable daily intake (TDI) of 0.186 µg/kg BW. Dividing exposure percentiles by the TDI gives the corresponding hazard index (HI) percentiles for risk characterisation.

Percentiles

Reference substance	Methylmercury (RF-00000169-CHE)
Hazard characterisation (µg/kg/day)	0.186
Mean exposure (µg/kg/day)	0.0256 [0.02414, 0.02949]
Mean hazard index	0.138 [0.13, 0.1588]

Percentiles hazard index.

Percentage	Exposure (µg/kg/day)	Exposure lower bound (p2.5)	Exposure upper bound (p97.5)	Hazard Index	Median (p50)	Lower bound (p2.5)	Upper bound (p97.5)
50.00	0.01067	0.009587	0.01125	0.05484	0.05745	0.05162	0.06059
90.00	0.0533	0.03684	0.07351	0.286	0.287	0.1984	0.3958
95.00	0.1256	0.09386	0.166	0.779	0.6762	0.5054	0.8938
99.00	0.2417	0.1935	0.3809	1.179	1.301	1.042	2.051
99.99	0.4243	0.3071	0.4637	2.285	2.285	1.654	2.497
99.99	0.4598	0.3285	0.4637	2.476	2.476	1.769	2.497

MCRA standard Action MeHg

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Concept > Creating a SA > Structure & Settings > Exercises > Solutions

Solutions

1) Calculate overall exposure (conventional production, consumers only, LB)

- (1) What is the mean and median exposure?
- (2) What is the HI at P50 and what does it mean?
- (3) What is the main contributing main food group?
- (4) What are the three main contributors at food level?

Exposures by modelled food (total distribution)

Total 20 modelled foods.

MCRA standard Action MeHg

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Concept > Creating a SA > Structure & Settings > Exercises > Solutions

Solutions

2) Calculate overall exposure (organic production, consumers only, LB)

(1) Do consumers with mainly organic food choice have lower or higher exposure?

Conventional

▼ Percentiles

Reference substance	Methylmercury (RF-00000169-CHE)
Hazard characterisation (µg/kg/day)	0.186
Mean exposure (µg/kg/day)	0.0256 [0.02414, 0.02949]
Mean hazard index	0.138 [0.13, 0.1588]

Percentiles hazard index.

Percentage	Exposure (µg/kg/day)	Exposure lower bound (p2.5)	Exposure upper bound (p97.5)
50.00	0.01067	0.009587	0.01125
90.00	0.0533	0.03684	0.07351
95.00	0.1256	0.09386	0.166
99.00	0.2417	0.1935	0.3809
99.90	0.4243	0.3071	0.4637
99.99	0.4598	0.3285	0.4637

Organic

▼ Percentiles

Reference substance	Methylmercury (RF-00000169-CHE)
Hazard characterisation (µg/kg/day)	0.186
Mean exposure (µg/kg/day)	0.0379 [0.0358, 0.04306]
Mean hazard index	0.204 [0.1928, 0.2319]

Percentiles hazard index.

Percentage	Exposure (µg/kg/day)	Exposure lower bound (p2.5)	Exposure upper bound (p97.5)
50.00	0.01118	0.01066	0.01312
90.00	0.08487	0.05853	0.1038
95.00	0.1771	0.1539	0.2057
99.00	0.413	0.3587	0.5124
99.90	0.7913	0.5256	0.8631
99.99	0.8599	0.5459	0.8631

MCRA standard Action MeHg

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Concept > Creating a SA > Structure & Settings > Exercises > Solutions

Solutions

3) Calculate regional exposure (just fish and seafood, consumers only, UB)

(1) What is the P95 exposure in North, East, South, West Germany?
 (2) Which is the main contributing food and how many individuals consume that food?

(1) **North:** 0,17 µg/g bw/d; **East:** 0,074 µg/g bw/d; **South:** 0,063 µg/g bw/d; **West:** 0,132 µg/g bw/d

(2) **North:** Rotbarsch (n=2); **East:** Fischstäbchen (n=22); **South:** Fischstäbchen (n=31); **West:** Pilzsuppen (n=4)

Example North:

Exposure statistics by modelled food (total distribution).

Food name	Food code	Contribution (%) mean	Contribution (%) lower bound (p2.5)	Contribution (%) upper bound (p97.5)	individuals with exposure	Mean exposure for all individuals (µg/kg bw/day)	n
Fischfilet überbacken	L0707	0.9	0.0	2.7	1	0.00031	1
Fischstäbchen	L0708	27.9	15.7	39.7	11	0.00711	11
Forelle	L0709	4.2	0.0	13.2	1	0.00103	1
Heilbutt geräuchert	L0714	1.5	0.0	6.0	1	0.000594	1
Heringsfilet in Soße	L0716	2.0	0.0	6.3	1	0.000546	1
Köhlner	L0719	3.3	0.6	6.2	5	0.00086	5
Lachs geräuchert	L0721	2.0	0.0	3.6	1	0.00051	1
Plattfische (Scholle, Saazunge)	L0722	1.6	0.0	4.5	1	0.000488	1
Rotbarsch	L0725	55.6	41.8	67.2	2	0.0188	2
Zuchtpilze	L0230	0.9	0.0	1.6	1	0.00022	1

MCRA standard Action MeHg

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Concept > Creating a SA > Structure & Settings > Exercises > Solutions

Solutions

4) Calculate seasonal exposure (mushrooms & products, consumers only, UB)

(1) In which season is the exposure the highest?

Winter Season

Percentiles hazard index.

Percentage	Exposure (µg/kg/day)	Exposure lower bound (p2.5)	Exposure upper bound (p97.5)	Hazard Index	Median (p50)	Lower bound (p2.5)	Upper bound (p97.5)
50.00	0.01823	0.005604	0.1378	0.1478	0.09815	0.0194	0.7421
90.00	0.1645	0.06812	0.1843	0.9578	0.8856	0.3668	0.9921
95.00	0.1991	0.1054	0.2283	1.229	1.072	0.5677	1.229
99.00	0.245	0.1556	0.3071	1.654	1.319	0.8377	1.654
99.90	0.2553	0.1668	0.3248	1.749	1.375	0.8984	1.749
99.99	0.2563	0.168	0.3266	1.759	1.38	0.9045	1.759

Mean: 0.0736 µg/kg bw/d

Summer Season

Percentiles hazard index.

Percentage	Exposure (µg/kg/day)	Exposure lower bound (p2.5)	Exposure upper bound (p97.5)	Hazard Index	Median (p50)	Lower bound (p2.5)	Upper bound (p97.5)
50.00	0.398	0.3586	0.8389	2.143	2.143	1.931	4.517
90.00	0.7442	0.4197	0.9128	4.208	4.607	2.26	4.915
95.00	0.8285	0.4299	0.9128	4.562	4.401	2.315	4.915
99.00	0.8959	0.438	0.9128	4.844	4.824	2.358	4.915
99.90	0.9111	0.4398	0.9128	4.908	4.906	2.368	4.915
99.99	0.9126	0.44	0.9128	4.914	4.914	2.369	4.915

Mean: 0.564 µg/kg bw/d

MCRA standard Action MeHg

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Concept > Creating a SA > Structure & Settings > Exercises > Solutions

Solutions

5) Calculate combined stratification exposure

(1) Do East German children consuming mushrooms and products thereof in winter are at risk of exceeding the TWI for MeHg?

(2) Where does the exposure come from?

(1) HI is <1 in each percentile. TWI is exceeded at HI >1

Percentiles hazard index.

Percentage	Exposure (µg/kg/day)	Exposure lower bound (p2.5)	Exposure upper bound (p97.5)	Hazard Index	Median (p50)	Lower bound (p2.5)	Upper bound (p97.5)
50.00	0.02467	0.02467	0.02467	0.1328	0.1328	0.1328	0.1328
90.00	0.02467	0.02467	0.02467	0.1328	0.1328	0.1328	0.1328
95.00	0.02467	0.02467	0.02467	0.1328	0.1328	0.1328	0.1328
99.00	0.02467	0.02467	0.02467	0.1328	0.1328	0.1328	0.1328
99.90	0.02467	0.02467	0.02467	0.1328	0.1328	0.1328	0.1328
99.99	0.02467	0.02467	0.02467	0.1328	0.1328	0.1328	0.1328

MCRA standard Action MeHg

page 20

Solutions

5) Calculate combined stratification exposure

- (1) Do East German children consuming mushrooms and products thereof in winter are at risk of exceeding the TWI for MeHg?
- (2) Where does the exposure come from?

(2) Exposure comes from the consumption of herring and cod

Note: There is just one consumer included in the combined stratification exposure

Exposure statistics by modelled food (total distribution).

Food name	Food code	Contribution (%) mean	Contribution (%) lower bound (p2.5)	Contribution (%) upper bound (p97.5)	individuals with exposure	Mean exposure for all individuals (µg/kg bw/day)
Heringsfilet in Soße	L0716	66.2	66.2	66.2	1	0.0163
Kabeljau	L0717	33.8	33.8	33.8	1	0.00935

Thank you for your attention

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Appendix 4 - Training materials TDS-exposure Belgian adults to nickel

 FACULTY OF BIOSCIENCE ENGINEERING

DEPARTMENT OF FOOD TECHNOLOGY, SAFETY AND HEALTH
FACULTY OF BIOSCIENCE ENGINEERING, GHEENT UNIVERSITY

DEMONSTRATION ON CONDUCTING RISK ASSESSMENT USING MCRA FOR THE UGENT CASE STUDY ON NICKEL

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 Rijksinstituut voor Volksgezondheid en Milieu
Ministerie van Volksgezondheid, Welzijn en Sport

 FACULTY OF BIOSCIENCE ENGINEERING

Outlines

- Background
- Data preparation for MCRA
- Risk assessment in MCRA
- Demonstration of results

 GHEENT UNIVERSITY

BACKGROUND

3

NICKEL ?

RELEVANCE OF NICKEL AS POTENTIAL FOOD SAFETY HAZARD ?

- ❖ A risk assessment of EFSA in 2015 stated that the occurrence of nickel in the diet is worrying for the general European population and for Ni-sensitive individuals (EFSA, 2015)

4

NICKEL-DATA

- Nickel concentration in foods → investigation conducted at UGent → Available in EFSA format (data owner)
- Belgian Food consumption data 2014 (BNFCS) → Sciensano → purchased by UGent for INNIBEL project and for FNS CLOUD project (no data owner)
- Risk assessment conducted at UGent → PhD thesis

STUDY CONDUCTED
AT UGENT

FOOD SAMPLES, SAMPLING PLAN AND ANALYSIS OF THE SAMPLES

- Risk-based sampling plan

- ❖ In total 708 samples
- ❖ Three major food categories:
- ❖ Plant-based foods (N = 406)
- ❖ Foods of animal origin (N = 113)
- ❖ Drinks (N = 189)

- Microwave-assisted acid digestion, ICP-MS analysis

7

EXPOSURE ASSESSMENT (METHOD)

- ❖ Ni screening data (main focus on plant based foods and drinks)
- ❖ Belgian food consumption data 2014
- ❖ Chronic exposure (two days consumers)

- ❖ Pooling : Food category or Food type
- ❖ Aggregated exposure assessment
- ❖ Simple distribution approach

8

PREPERAING THE INPUT DATA FOR MCRA TESTING

9

MCRA MODULE → DATA FORMAT

Creation of three MCRA datasets containing the necessary data for running the scenarios in MCRA:

- 1) A consumptions dataset based on the BNFCS data
- 2) A concentrations dataset derived from the INNIBEL concentration data
- 3) A catalogue dataset containing the catalogues and additional data

10

- The table below describes these datasets, together with the MCRA data groups and data tables that make up these datasets:

Dataset	MCRA Data type	Data table	Mapping method
Catalogues FNS Case Study Nickel BE population	Populations	Populations	Manual creation.
		IndividualProperties	Manual creation.
		PopulationIndividualPropertyValues	Manual creation.
	Foods	Foods	Manual creation.
	Substances	Substances	Manual creation.
	Effects	Effects	Manual creation.
BNFCS 2014-2015 (FoodNum)	Consumptions	Surveys	Manual creation.
		Individuals	Automatic import with Access SQL queries.
		Consumptions	Automatic import with Access SQL queries.
		Concentrations (INIBEL)	ConcentrationsSSD

FOOD CONSUMPTION DATA

FoodNum catalogue UGent to MCRA format

- The catalogue of of the FoodNum
- FoodNum Code Food Name
- 02184 Tofu/Tofoe
- 00002 Aardappelen/Pomme de terre
- 01296 Chocolade, melk/Chocolat, au lait

FOOD CONSUMPTION DATA

- Translation of FoodNum codes to FoodEx2 codes
- For making the data available for MCRA, The FoodEx2 codes have been converted to FoodNum codes to combine food consumption data and concentration data.

Table FoodTranslation

Column name	Description
idFromFood	FoodNum code
idToFood	FoodEx2 code
Proportion	always 100%

RISK ASSESSMENT IN MCRA 9.1

Appendix 5 - Training materials Acute cumulative exposure to pesticides

Rijksinstituut voor Volksgezondheid
en Milieu
Ministerie van Volksgezondheid,
Welzijn en Sport

Concept

Mixtures of pesticides

Concept cumulative dietary exposure assessment pesticides

Content

- Final methodology cumulative exposure assessment pesticides concept according to EFSA guidance - who is responsible for what
- Understanding the concept and data used in Tier II calculations
- Exercise use case Tier II calculations

2

Concept cumulative dietary exposure assessment pesticides

The role of DG SANTE

The legal basis

Article 14 of **Regulation (EC) No 396/2005** provides that pesticide MRL setting needs to *'take account of their known cumulative and synergistic effects, when the methods to assess such effects are available'*

Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009, Article 4
"Residues of the plant protection products shall not have any harmful effects on human health or animal health, *taking into account known cumulative and synergistic effects where the scientific methods accepted by the Authority to assess such effects are available.*"

3 Concept cumulative dietary exposure assessment pesticides

EFSA conclusions of retrospective CRA published in 2020

EFSA JOURNAL

Scientific Report |

Cumulative dietary risk characterisation of pesticides that have acute effects on the nervous system

European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) Peter S Craig, Bruno Dujardin, Andy Hart, Antonio F Hernandez-jerez, Susanne Hougaard Bennekou, Carsten Kneuer. ... [See all authors](#) -

First published: 29 April 2020 | <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2020.6087> | Citations: 1

EFSA JOURNAL

Scientific Report |

Cumulative dietary risk characterisation of pesticides that have chronic effects on the thyroid

European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) Peter S Craig, Bruno Dujardin, Andy Hart, Antonio F Hernandez-jerez, Susanne Hougaard Bennekou, Carsten Kneuer. ... [See all authors](#) -

First published: 29 April 2020 | <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2020.6088>

<https://efsa.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.2903/j.efsa.2020.6087>
<https://efsa.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.2903/j.efsa.2020.6088>

Concept cumulative dietary exposure assessment pesticides

Exposure assessment methods

Random sampling from a concentration and a consumption database

DG SANTE in cooperation with Member States decided on the tiers in SCo PAFF meeting

ANNEX I: Table of agreed assumptions required to be included in the two technical reports

WDv7§	Assumption	Calculations
3.2	>Margin Of Exposure >Percentile of exposure distribution	MOE=100 P99.9 (whole population approach, §3.5.2.1)
3.5.3.1 3.5.1.2	Non-Quantified Residues	Tier 1: For datasets with at least one finding, replace NQs with 1/2 LOQ, regardless of authorizations and also take into account Processing Factors. Ideally make use of the full distribution of values, if available, else medians. Include information from EFSA & BFR data. Tier 2: Calculations based on Option 6 of the Commission working document.
3.5.3.3	Processing Factors (PF)	Tiers 1 & 2 use PF distribution all sources, otherwise medians (see above)
3.5.3.4	Pesticide Residues in Water	Tier 1: 0.1µg/L for the 5 most potent substances of the CAG. Tier 2: 0.05µg/L for the 5 most potent substances of the CAG.
3.5.4	Variability Factor (VF)	Acute Exposure Tier 1: b-distribution, VFs from PRIMO model. Acute Exposure Tier 2: b-distribution, VF= 3.5
3.5.1.1	MRL exceedances	Agreement that samples exceeding MRLs should be taken into account resulting into a more realistic approach
3.5.2.1	Consumers-Only or Whole-Population	Whole Population approach (as indicated for §3.2)

http://www.efsa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/SANTE_CRA_Mandate.pdf

6
Concept cumulative dietary exposure assessment pesticides

Data used in exposure assessment

- Official monitoring results from National Competent Authorities 2014-2016 as delivered to EFSA
- Use individual consumption data from Member States
- National food consumption surveys from various Member States (10 diets in PRIMo expressed as Raw Primary Commodity)

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Concept cumulative dietary exposure assessment pesticides

Models used in exposure assessment

Use Monte Carlo Risk Assessment Software (MCRA) software or SAS software

- Select monitoring samples at random
- Multiply residue levels from monitoring with each consumed food item
- Include processing factors
- Include variability factors
- Residue definition

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Concept cumulative dietary exposure assessment pesticides

How to weigh toxicity of each pesticide in the exposure assessment?

The toxicity of pesticides is weighed based on the Relative Potency Factor (RPF)

Although the concentration of Pirimiphos-methyl is higher compared to Dichlorvos, the contribution to the exposure is lower. This is explained by the RPF which is 100 x lower

Substance	Concentration in sample (mg/kg)	Exposure (µg/kg bw/day)	RPF	% of total
Dichlorvos	0.16	0.93	1.00	87
Omethoate	0.0581	0.19	0.40	7
Pirimiphos-methyl	0.65	3.76	0.01	2

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Concept cumulative dietary exposure assessment pesticides

Information on processing factors

The pesticide monitoring is focused on raw primary commodities e.g. apples.

However, apples might be processed in many different foods as eaten e.g. apple juice, apple pie

Pesticide concentration will change during processing

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Concept cumulative dietary exposure assessment pesticides

Exposure results expressed as MOET

- MOET stands for Margin of Exposure Total. Total refers to all pesticides in the CAG.
- The Commission decided to look at the P99.9 of the exposure distribution
- It starts from a No-Adverse-Effect Level (No(A)EL) in animal experiments. This value is multiplied with a factor 10 covering the uncertainty extrapolating from animal studies to humans. An additional safety factor of 10 accounts for variation in sensitivity to the effect.
- The MOET should ideally be more than 100

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Concept cumulative dietary exposure assessment pesticides

Results Margin Of Exposure Total (MOET)

Pesticides associated with brain and/or erythrocyte AChE inhibition (CAG- NAN)
Pesticides associated with functional alterations of the motor division (CAG-NAM)

Country	Population class	MOET, 99.9 th percentile of exposure	
		Nervous system (acute effect)	
		NAN	NAM
Belgium	Adults	102	176
Czech Republic	Adults	120	172
Germany	Adults	95	171
Italy	Adults	96	141
Bulgaria	Other Children	49	63
France	Other Children	59	84
The Netherlands	Other Children	52	89
Denmark	Toddlers	60	80
The Netherlands	Toddlers	40	68
United Kingdom	Toddlers	61	73

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Concept cumulative dietary exposure assessment pesticides

3.2 Training materials explanation of the demonstrator

Rijksinstituut voor Volksgezondheid en Milieu
Ministerie van Volksgezondheid, Welzijn en Sport

Tier II acute cumulative

Pesticides

October 2021

v

Learning goal and context

- This training will enable you to reproduce the exposure assessment of cumulative effects of pesticide residues in food. These are retrospective exposure assessments of the cumulative risks for the nervous system using monitoring data from 2014, 2015 and 2016 and are reported in a scientific report following the methodology published by EFSA in September 2019/20 and accepted by the European Commission. When available you can use your own consumption data.
 - <https://efsa.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/epdf/10.2903/sp.efsa.2019.EN-1708>
- More information on the EFSA cumulative dietary risk characterisation of pesticides that have acute effects on the nervous system can be found on the EFSA website. The exposure assessments were conducted as part of a sequential process; 1) establishment of cumulative assessment groups, 2) exposure assessment, 3) risk characterisation and uncertainty.
 - <https://efsa.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.2903/j.efsa.2020.6087>

2 October 2021

Learning goal and context

- This training will enable you to reproduce the exposure assessment of cumulative effects of pesticide residues in food. These are retrospective exposure assessments of the cumulative risks for the nervous system using monitoring data from 2014, 2015 and 2016 and are reported in a scientific report following the methodology published by EFSA in September 2019/20 and accepted by the European Commission. When available you can use your own consumption data.

- <https://efsa.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/epdf/10.2903/sp.efsa.2019.EN-1708>

- More information on the EFSA cumulative dietary risk characterisation of pesticides that have acute effects on the nervous system can be found on the EFSA website. The exposure assessments were conducted as part of a sequential process; 1) establishment of cumulative assessment groups, 2) exposure assessment, 3) risk characterisation and uncertainty.

- <https://efsa.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.2903/j.efsa.2020.6087>

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MCRA

- <https://mcra.rivm.nl>
- MCRA 9.1

Welcome to MCRA

Please select the version of MCRA that you wish to use.

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October 2021

The screenshot shows the MCRA 9.1 login page. At the top, there is a blue header with the UK Royal Coat of Arms. Below the header, the word "Login" is displayed in blue. A bullet point lists "Login" or register for an account, with "Login" circled in red. The page content includes a "Welcome to MCRA 9.1" section, a brief description of MCRA, and information about its development. A "Register for an account" button is visible, along with a "Log in here" link that is also circled in red. There are also buttons for "MCRA documentation" and "Publications and reports using MCRA". The footer of the page shows the number "5" and the date "October 2021".

5 October 2021

The screenshot shows the MCRA 9.1 login form. At the top, there is a blue header with the UK Royal Coat of Arms. Below the header, the word "Login" is displayed in blue. A bullet point lists "Login - using your own username and password". The form itself has a blue header with "Log in" and two input fields: "Username *" and "Password *". Both fields have red error messages: "Username is required" and "Password is required". Below the input fields is a "Login" button. At the bottom of the form, there are links for "Forgot password" and "Create an account". The footer of the page shows the number "6" and the date "October 2021".

6 October 2021

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Create workspace

- Select workspaces

Welcome to MCRA 9.1
Chemical exposure, hazard and risk assessment

MCRA can perform 51 **action types**, for example dietary exposure assessment, dose response modelling, hazard characterisation and risk assessment. Actions are structured in a network of modules.

Use **workspaces** to create or clone **actions** of a specific action type, by providing data and settings. Actions may need subactions of other action types. You can run the main action or any of its subactions. Actions can be fully customised by the MCRA user, but for simplified use a series of **standard actions** is being developed.

After running an action or subaction, **results** are available. Results are in the form of screen reports, print reports and/or tables for download, and may also include output data that are useful as input for other actions.

Data are organised in a data repository, which includes shared folders from other users and user groups.

Start by clicking **Workspaces** or **Data**

8 October 2021

Create workspace

- Create workspace by clicking +
- Give the workspace a name (e.g. EuroMix training acute cum)
- Click on OK

MCRA 9.1
Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment

Workspaces

Name	Last modified	Tags
------	---------------	------

Create new workspace

Create a new workspace, please provide a descriptive name.

workspace name *

OK Cancel

The image shows two screenshots of the FNS Cloud interface. The top screenshot, labeled '9' in the bottom left corner, shows the 'Create standard action' page. It features a navigation bar with 'Actions', 'Data', 'Results', and 'Properties'. Below the navigation bar is a 'Workspace actions' section with '(51 selected)' and a dropdown menu. A message states 'This workspace does not contain actions.' A green '+' button is circled in red, and a red arrow points to a dropdown menu containing three options: 'Create action', 'Create standard action', and 'Import action from zip file'. The bottom screenshot, labeled '10' in the bottom left corner, shows the same 'Create standard action' page. A bullet point indicates the selection of 'EuroMix Follow-up acute cumulative exposure assessment (2018) Tier II'. Below this, a modal window titled 'Create new standard action' is open, showing a list of standard action types. The selected option is circled in red. The modal window contains the following text: 'Select standard action type', 'EuroMix Follow-up acute cumulative exposure assessment (2018) Tier II', and a detailed description: 'This standard action will enable you to calculate the exposure assessment of cumulative effects of pesticide residues in food affecting the nervous system. These are retrospective exposure assessments of the cumulative exposure for the nervous system using monitoring data from 2014, 2015 and 2016. The methodology is reported in a scientific report following published on the EFSA website in September 2019. The methodology fulfils the requirements set by the European Commission.'

Create standard action

- You can adjust the name and enter tags / description
- Click on 'Create'

Create new standard action

Specify name/description

General

Name
EuroMix Follow-up acute cumulative exposure assessment (2018) Tier II

Tags

Description
Training Acute cumulative exposure assessment

Back Create

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Settings

- Select Effect: NAN

Assessment settings

Effect
Country
Age group
Uncertainty analysis
No uncertainty

Save Changes

NAN
NAM

NAN: Neurotoxic acute: AChE inhibition – 47 substances
NAM: Neurotoxic acute: motor division – 100 substances

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Country and age group (1)

- Consumption data were extracted by EFSA from the RPC consumption database
 - For more information regarding the raw primary commodity model see: <https://efsa.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.2903/sp.efsa.2019.EN-1532>

- RPC data received from EFSA:

Country	Age group
Czech republic	4-65 yr
Denmark	4-75+ yr
	0-4 yr
Italy	0-75+ yr
Netherlands	7-70 yr
	2-7 yr
	70+ yr
Sweden	18-75+ yr

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October 2021

Country and age group (2)

- In the EFSA report of 2019, calculations were done for 3 age groups:
 - Toddlers (1-3 yr)
 - Other children (3-10 yr)
 - Adults (18-65 yr)

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Settings

- Select country: e.g. Czech Republic
- Select an age group: e.g. Adults (18-65 yr)
- Save Changes

Assessment settings

Effect	NAN	
Country	Czech Republic	
Age group	Adults (18-65yr)	
Uncertainty analysis	No uncertainty	

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Run standard action

- Run action by clicking

The screenshot shows a software window titled 'EuroMix Follow-up acute cumulative exposure assessment (2018) Tier II'. The 'Settings' section is highlighted in green. The 'Run standard action' button is circled in red. The 'Assessment settings' section shows 'Effect: NAN'.

Rename standard action

- You can rename action by clicking
- Rename and click on 'OK'

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Results (1)

- Click on the name to view the results

Results

Output	Status	Message
CZ-Adults-18-65yr-NAN-NoUnc	Ran to completion	

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Results (2)

MCRA 9.1 / Euromix training a... / EuroMix Follow-up
Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment workspace action

EuroMix Follow-up acute cumulative exposure assessment (2018) Tier II
Standard action - EuroMix Follow-up acute cumulative exposure assessment (2018) Tier II

Results / CZ-Adults-18-65yr-NAN

Results
Settings

- ▼ EU acute cumulative exposure assessment (2018)
- ▼ Settings

Setting name	Value
Effect	NAN
Country	CZ
Age group	Adults-18-65yr
Uncertainty analysis	No uncertainty

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Results (3)

- Margin of exposure ○
- Food/substances contributing to the upper tail ○

? ?

Percentiles margin of exposure.

Percentage exposure	Exposure (µg/kg bw/day)	Percentage MOE	Margin of exposure
99.99	2.501	0.01	39.72
99.90	0.6635	0.10	149.8
99.00	0.146	1.00	684.4
95.00	0.07678	5.00	1302
90.00	0.06322	10.00	1582
50.00	0.03378	50.00	2960

▼ Upper tail exposures by food and substance

Total 113 combinations of foods and substance with contribution in the upper tail, bw/day, maximum value 25.78 µg/kg bw/day.

Contribution to the upper tail distribution for modelled foods x substances (MSCC).

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Results (4)

- Use EmptyTemplateReportingResults.xlsx
- Report the cumulative margin of exposure percentiles
- Report the risk drivers: top 5 food/substances contributing the most to the upper tail of the distribution

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Format occurrence data (1)

- You might want to use data from your own country
 - Occurrence data: search (google) zenodo pesticides <country name>

zenodo pesticides netherlands

[Alle](#) [Nieuws](#) [Afbeeldingen](#) [Maps](#) [Shopping](#) [Meer](#)

Ongeveer 17.800 resultaten (0,30 seconden)

<https://zenodo.org/record/> [Vertaal deze pagina](#)

Dutch results from the monitoring of pesticide residues in food

8 mei 2020 — Knowledge Junction. License (for files): Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International. Versions. Version 5 10.5281/zenodo.5021817, Jun 24, ...

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Format occurrence data (2)

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Format occurrence data (3)

Name	Type	Description	Alias	Required
labSampleCode	AlphaNumeric(30)	Code of the laboratory sample. MCRA will use the combination of labSampleCode and labSubSampleCode as unique code for a sample.	labSampleCode	Yes
labSubSampleCode	AlphaNumeric(4)	Code of the laboratory sub-sample. MCRA will use the combination of labSampleCode and labSubSampleCode as unique code for a sample.	labSubSampleCode	No
sampleCountry	AlphaNumeric(2)	Two-letter code to identify the country of sampling.	sampleCountry	Yes

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2. Occurrence data

Format Table ConcentrationsSSD

Field Name	Data Type
labSampCode	Short Text
labSubSampCode	Short Text
sampCountry	Short Text
prodCode	Short Text
sampP	Number
sampM	Number
sampD	Number
analysisY	Number
analysisM	Number
analysisD	Number
paramCode	Short Text
resUnit	Short Text
resLOD	Number
resLOQ	Number
resVal	Number
resType	Short Text

Content Table ConcentrationsSSD												
labSampCode	labSubSampCode	paramCode	sampP	sampM	sampD	analysisY	analysisM	analysisD	resUnit	resLOD	resVal	resType
90426790	0	XX	P011802EA	2018	1	15	2018	1	15	8F-0004822-P-0001A	0.005	LOQ
750426790	0	XX	P011802EA	2018	1	15	2018	1	15	8F-0004822-P-0001A	0.005	LOQ
750426790	0	XX	P011802EA	2018	1	15	2018	1	15	8F-0412-001-P-0001A	0.005	LOQ
80228960	0	XX	P020001EA	2018	10	2	2018	10	2	8F-0230-001-P-0001A	0.005	LOQ
80228960	0	XX	P020001EA	2018	10	2	2018	10	2	8F-0004822-P-0001A	0.005	0.812 VAL
80228960	0	XX	P020001EA	2018	10	2	2018	10	2	8F-0412-001-P-0001A	0.005	LOQ
80217920	0	XX	P021201EA	2018	8	20	2018	8	20	8F-0250-001-P-0001A	0.005	LOQ
80217920	0	XX	P021201EA	2018	8	20	2018	8	20	8F-0004822-P-0001A	0.005	LOQ
80217920	0	XX	P021201EA	2018	8	20	2018	8	20	8F-0412-001-P-0001A	0.005	LOQ
80442070	0	XX	P016802EA	2018	6	12	2018	6	12	8F-0230-001-P-0001A	0.005	LOQ
80442070	0	XX	P016802EA	2018	6	12	2018	6	12	8F-0004822-P-0001A	0.005	LOQ
80442070	0	XX	P016802EA	2018	6	12	2018	6	12	8F-0412-001-P-0001A	0.005	LOQ
80442070	0	XX	P016802EA	2018	4	16	2018	4	16	8F-0230-001-P-0001A	0.005	8.0053 VAL
80442070	0	XX	P016802EA	2018	4	16	2018	4	16	8F-0004822-P-0001A	0.005	LOQ
80442070	0	XX	P016802EA	2018	4	16	2018	4	16	8F-0412-001-P-0001A	0.005	LOQ
80442073	0	XX	P011801EA	2018	4	16	2018	4	16	8F-0250-001-P-0001A	0.005	8.2 VAL
80442073	0	XX	P011801EA	2018	4	16	2018	4	16	8F-0004822-P-0001A	0.005	LOQ
80442073	0	XX	P011801EA	2018	4	16	2018	4	16	8F-0412-001-P-0001A	0.005	LOQ

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Format consumption data (1)

- Consumptions received from EFSA: Consumption data converted using the RPC model
- After permission of the person responsible for consumption data of CZ, DK, AT, IT, SE, NL, EFSA was asked to send the RPC data of these countries to us.

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Format consumption data (2)

Modules

- Primary entity modules
- Consumption modules
 - Consumptions
 - Consumptions data formats
 - Consumptions calculation
 - Consumptions settings
 - Consumptions uncertainty
- Food recipes
- Market shares
- Single value consumptions
- Occurrence modules
- Exposure modules
- Hazard modules
- In-silico modules
- Kinetic modules
- Risk modules

TextValue	AlphaNumeric(50)	The value of the property as text value.	No
DoubleValue	Numeric	The value of the property as number.	No

Consumptions

The individual consumptions are recorded in the consumptions table.

Table aliases: FoodConsumptions, FoodConsumption, Consumptions, Consumption.

Table 30 : Table definition for Consumptions

Name	Type	Description	Aliases	Required
idIndividual	AlphaNumeric(50)	The unique identification code of the consumer (Individual).	idIndividual, IndividualId, Individual	Yes
idFood	AlphaNumeric(50)	The food code (food as eaten code).	idFood, Food, FoodId, FoodConsumed, FoodAsEaten	Yes

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1. Consumption data - format

Table Consumptions

Field Name	Data Type	Constraints
idIndividual	Text	required, size 50
idFood	Text	required, size 50
idUnit	Text	optional, size 50
idDay	Text	required
idMeal	Text	optional
Amount	Number	required
DateConsumed	Date/Time	

Reported consumed foods per individual

Table Food

Field Name	Data Type	Constraints
Food	Text	required, size 50
Foodname	Text	optional, size 100

Foods consumed

Table Individuals

Field Name	Data Type	Constraints
idIndividual	Text	required, size 50
idFoodSurvey	Text	required, size 50
BodyWeight	Number	optional
SamplingWeight	Number	required
NumberOfSurveyDays	Number	optional
Age	Number	optional
Gender	Text	optional, size 50
AnotherIndividualProperty	Number	optional

Personal information per individual

Table FoodSurveys

Field Name	Data Type	Constraints
idFoodSurvey	Text	required, size 50
Description	Text	optional, size 200
Location	Text	optional, size 50
BodyWeightUnit	Text	optional, size 50, default kg
AgeUnit	Text	optional, size 50
ConsumptionUnit	Text	optional, size 50, default g
StartDate	Date/Time	optional
EndDate	Date/Time	optional
NumberOfSurveyDays	Number	required

FoodConsumption survey information

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1. Consumption data – example of the content

Table Consumptions

IndividualId	FoodId	DayId	MealId	Amount
180613666	A.01.07.001.024	1		50
180613666	A.01.07.001.024	2		60
180613666	A.02.01.004	1		2.3479418900
180613666	A.02.04.006	1		140.2112625
180613666	A.03.01.006	1		254.929581833
180613666	A.03.02.021	1		70
180613666	A.03.01.005	1		17.5
180613666	A.05.02.001	1		19.8377
180613666	A.06.02.001	1		12.2449
180613666	A.06.08.007	2		19
180613666	A.06.09.004	1		129
180613666	A.08.02.001.001	1		274.7
180613666	A.08.06.001.002	1		118.8
180613666	A.08.06.001.003	2		178.2

Table Food

FoodId	FoodName
A.05.01.004	Limes (Citrus aurantifolia)
A.05.01.005	Mandarins (Citrus reticulata)
A.05.01.006	Pomelo (Citrus grandis)
A.05.02	Pome fruits
A.05.02.001	Apple (Malus domestica)
A.05.02.002	Pear (Pyrus communis)
A.05.02.003	Quince (Cydonia oblonga)
A.05.02.004	Medlar (Mespilus germanica)

Table Individuals

IdIndividual	IdFoodSurvey	BodyWeight	SamplingWeight	NumberOfSurveyDays	Age	Gender
180613666	FoodSurvey	72	1.2	2	50	1

Table FoodSurvey

IdFoodSurvey	Description	Location	BodyWeightUnit	AgeUnit	ConsumptionUnit	StartDate	EndDate	NumberOfSurveyDays
FoodSurvey	Food consumption survey	NL	KG	YR	G	01/01/2013	01/01/2014	2

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Appendix 6 – User Manuals Low-end user app: user guidance for Data providers

PREPARATION OF DATASETS FOR PUBLISHING

The application was developed with the purposes to support institutions publishing their TDS data and to inform low-end users about contents of substances in foods (based on results of TDS). In order to publish TDS data by the low end-user app, datasets need to be transmitted in a particular data format to enable an easy import to the web application. Various data and information are needed which are categorized as follows:

- 1) Data and information essential for the publication of TDS datasets by the app (analyzed foods and substances, analytical limits, results, translation tables, short description of the respective TDS) (**“Required”**)
- 2) Data and information that is not imperatively required (population-based dietary exposure levels, contribution of food groups to dietary exposure). This additional information apart from the content tables is meant to be essential to increase understandability and information content. Therefore, the provision is highly recommended under the aspect of risk communication. In case that the information is not available for the respective TDS, it is conceivable to use respective information from EFSA opinions or statements (by naming the source) (**“Optional”**)

The data format on concentrations from Total Diet studies is orientated on the data structure of the German BfR MEAL study. The MEAL study is considered to be one of the most complex TDS, so the structure should also be applicable to most other TDS. Of course, information (e. g. on regions or season) can also be omitted/simplified if these were not distinguished in other TDSs.

Content data table (Required)

The TDS food content data table contains descriptions of TDS foods (+ groups), analysed substances, analytical limits and results.

Table aliases: food_content_data

File format: .xls, .csv

Name	Description	Format	Aliases	Example
Food Code	The unique identification code of the food. Food can be coded after FoodEx2 or dataset-specific (translation in table food_translation).	Sequence of digits and/or letters	food_id	0901
Food Group Code	The unique identification code of the food group. Food can be coded after FoodEx2 or dataset-specific (translation in table food_group_translation).	Sequence of digits and/or letters	food_group_id	09
Substance Code	The unique identification code of the substance (e. g. acronym of the substance)	Sequence of digits and/or letters	substance_id	Al
Region (English)	Region in which samples were collected in English.	text	region_EN	north/ east/ south/ west
Region (National language(s))	Region in which samples were collected in the national language(s).	text	region_XX (instead of XX: national	[...]

			language; e. g. region_DE)	
Season (English)	Season of sampling in English.	text	season_EN	summer/ winter
Season (National language(s))	Season of sampling in the national language(s).	text	season_XX (instead of XX: national language; e. g. season_DE)	[...]
Organic	Is the substance considered as organic.	Boolean value	organic	1 (True)/ 0 (false)
LOD	Limit of detection; lowest concentration that can be detected; given by the particular analytical method.	number	LOD	0,006
LOQ	Limit of quantification; lowest concentration that can be quantified; given by the particular analytical method.	number	LOQ	0,018
Unit	The unit of the result/ LOD, LOQ (must all be the same for each substance)	text	result_unit	mg/ 100 g
Result	Average content data for the specific substance and food.	number	result	0,0332
Value type	Value type of the result.	Available options: BELOW_LOD, BELOW_LOQ, MEASURED, VAL	value_type	MEASURED

Translation tables (Required)

Translation tables include the names of coded foods (+groups), substances (+groups) in English and/or national language(s). If more than one national language should be included, for each language a separate column is needed (e. g. food_name_DE). Translation in English is highly recommended in order to make data understandable for an international audience.

File format: .xls, .csv

Food translation

In the content data table, foods are coded with a unique identification code. These coding can be but must not be in accordance to FoodEx2. Either way, translation of the codes needs to be provided in English and/or the national language(s).

Table aliases: food_translation

Name	Description	Format	Aliases	Example
Food Code	The unique identification code of the food. The provided food code should match with the code of the content data table.	Sequence of digits and/or letters	food_id	0901

Food Name (English)	The name of the food in English.	text	food_name_EN	Apple
Food Name (National language(s))	The name of the food in the national language(s).	text	food_name_XX (instead of XX: national language; e. g. food_name_DE)	[...]

Food group translation

In the content data table, foods are arranged into food groups and food groups are coded with a unique identification code. These coding can be but must not be in accordance to FoodEx2. Either way, translation of the codes needs to be provided in English and/or the national language(s).

Table aliases: food_group_translation

Name	Description	Format	Aliases	Example
Food Group Code	The unique identification code of the food group. Food can be coded after FoodEx2 or dataset-specific. The provided food group code should match with the code of the content data table.	Sequence of digits and/or letters	food_group_id	09
Food Group Name (English)	The name of the food group in English.	text	food_group_name_EN	Fruit and fruit products
Food Group Name (National language(s))	The name of the food group in the national language(s).	text	food_group_name_XX (instead of XX: national language; e. g. food_group_name_DE)	[...]

Substance translation

In the content data table, substances are coded with a unique identification code. This coding is dataset-specific and needs a translation in English and/or the national language(s).

Table aliases: substance_translation

Name	Description	Format	Aliases	Example
Substance Code	The unique identification code of the substance. The provided substance code should match with the code of the content data table.	Sequence of digits and/or letters	substance_id	Al

Substance Name (English)	The name of the substance in English.	text	substance_name_EN	Aluminium
Substance Description (English)	Description of the substance in English, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Occurrence of the substance (e. g. natural occurring substance) • Entry path into the foods (e. g. naturally, part of food additives or food contact materials) • Significance for humans (e. g. essentiell) 	text	substance_description_EN	Aluminium is one of the most common elements on earth ¹ and therefore a natural occurring element in soil. It is released by natural processes and anthropogenic activities such as mining and industrial uses ² . Food is the major source for aluminium exposure, both as a consequence of the natural occurrence of aluminium in food, and the use of aluminium food additives and food contact materials ² .
Substance Name (National language(s))	The name of the substance in the national language(s).	text	substance_name_XX (instead of XX: national language; e. g. substance_name_DE)	[...]
Substance Description (National language(s))	The description of the substance in the national language(s). As above	text	substance_description_XX	[...]
Substance Group Code	The unique identification code of the substance group. As there are no general substance groups, substance groups (+codes) are dataset-specific.	Sequence of digits and/or letters	substance_group_id	SG1
Dietary reference value (English)	Dietary reference value, defined for the respective substance (preferable taken from EFSA), type (e. g. AI), age/population group	text	dietary_reference_value_EN	1,3 mg day ⁻¹ (women) ³ 1,6 mg day ⁻¹ (men) ³ (AI)

Dietary reference value (National language(s))	Dietary reference value, in the national language(s). As above	text	dietary_reference_value_XX (instead of XX: national language; e. g. dietary_reference_value_DE)	[...]
Toxicological reference value (English)	Toxicological reference value, defined for the respective substance (preferable taken from EFSA), type (e. g. UL), age/population group	number+unit	tox_reference_value_EN	1 mg kg ⁻¹ bw week ⁻¹ (TWI) ² (adults, children)
Toxicological reference value (National language(s))	Toxicological reference value, in the national language(s). As above	text	tox_reference_value_XX (instead of XX: national language; e. g. tox_reference_value_DE)	[...]
Further information	The field can contain additional information, like references for reference values	text	further_information	¹ Stellungnahme BfR: Reduzierung der Aluminiumaufnahme kann mögliche Gesundheitsrisiken minimieren (2019) https://www.bfr.bund.de/cm/343/reduzierung-der-aluminiumaufnahme-kann-moegliche-gesundheitsrisiken-mindern.pdf ² EFSA Journal 2008; 754, 1-34 https://efsa.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/epdf/10.2903/j.efsa.2008.754
Substance Essential	Information if substance is considered as essential for the human body	Boolean value	substance_essential	1 (True)/ 0 (false)

Substance group translation

Substances are arranged into substance groups and substance groups are coded with a unique identification code. This coding is dataset-specific and needs a translation in English and/or the national language(s).

Table aliases: substance_group_translation

Name	Description	Format	Aliases	Example
Substance Group Code	The unique identification code of the substance group. The provided substance group code should match with the code of the content data table.	Sequence of digits and/or letters	substance_group_id	SG5
Substance Group Name (English)	The name of the substance group in English.	text	substance_group_name_EN	Food additives
Substance Group Description (English)	Definition of the substance group in English (e. g. taken from EFSA Glossary)	text	substance_group_description_EN	Food additives are substances added intentionally to foodstuffs to perform certain technological functions, for example to colour, to sweeten or to help preserve foods ¹ .
Substance Group Name (National language(s))	The name of the substance group in the national language(s).	text	substance_group_name_XX (instead of XX: national language; e. g. substance_group_name_DE)	[...]
Substance Group Description (National language(s))	As above	text	substance_group_description_XX (instead of XX: national language; e. g. substance_group_description_DE)	[...]
Substance Group Reference		text	substance_group_reference	¹ https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/topics/topic/food-additive-re-evaluations

Short description of the study (Required)

As Total Diet Studies are mainly unknown by the public and by the potential users, the app will provide some basic information about the respective study. For interested users, further information are available as links to corresponding webpages, publications or other relevant information sources. Information can be provided in English and/or national language(s).

Table aliases: dataset_description

Name	Description	Format	Aliases	Example
Name Dataset (English)	Name of the TDS	text	dataset_name_EN	TDS Exposure
Name Dataset (National language(s))	Name of the TDS	text	dataset_name_XX (instead of XX: national language; e. g. dataset_name_DE)	[...]
Description Dataset (English)	Description of the TDS, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Where the study was conducted and by whom? •When? •Key data (e. g. how many substances, foods, underlying consumption survey, covered age groups) •Special features (e. g. stratifications) •Country, where the TDS was conducted •Name of the institution(s) who conducted the TDS 	text (a maximum of 1,500 characters, including spaces)	dataset_description_EN	<p>The TDS-Exposure-Study is a pilot total diet study in Germany, performed 2014-2015 by the German Federal Institute for risk assessment (BfR) as part of the European TDS-Exposure project. This study provides data regarding concentration of selected heavy metals (aluminum, copper, mercury, manganese, lead) in the most frequently consumed food in Germany based on the consumption habits of the adult population (14-80 years).</p> <p>Following the principles of Total Diet Studies (TDS), foods were selected on basis of representative consumption data sets (National Consumption Survey II (NVSII)). Besides covering the most frequently consumed foods (> 90%), foods less consumed but known for high contents of considered substances were included. Foods were collected in the Berlin area, prepared as usually consumed, pooled and homogenized before being analyzed for the selected substances.</p>
Description Dataset (National language(s))	As above, in national language(s)	text	dataset_description_XX (instead of XX: national language; e. g. dataset_description_DE)	[...]
Dataset References	relevant references (e. g. publications, corresponding webpages etc.) and links, if available	text	dataset_references_EN	Kolbaum et al. (2019): Dietary exposure to elements from the German pilot total diet study (TDS). Food Additives & Contaminants: Part A, 36:12, 1822-1836. DOI: 10.1080/19440049.2019.1668967

				https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/289108 /forschungsprojekte/nvsii/
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Short statement (Optional)

As optional information, the provision of a short “easy-to-understand”- statement is highly recommended, including a comparison of toxicological reference values for the respective substance with population-based dietary intake estimates based on the presented data.

The short statement is preferable based on evaluations of the respective dataset but, if data or analyses are not available, texts can also be taken from opinions or statements from other institutions, preferable the EFSA (quoting the reference).

The Statement table contains the substance code, a short statement and references if available. Information can be provided in English and/or national language(s).

Table aliases: substance_statement

File format: .xls, .csv

Name	Description	Format	Aliases	Example
Substance Code	The unique identification code of the substance. The provided food code should match with the code of the content data table.	Sequence of digits and/or letters	substance_id	Al
Statement (English)	Short „easy-to-understand“ statement: whether toxicological reference values are reached with regard to the population-based exposure assessments; e. g. taken from official statements that are already published	text (a maximum of 500 characters, including spaces)	substance_statement_EN	For the adult population in Germany, the estimated average exposure to aluminium is between 0.18-0,21 mg/ kg bw per week for mean consumption and 0.42-0.44 mg/kg bw per week for high consumption. Assuming a body weight of 70 kg, the calculated intake levels accounted for 18-21% of the TWI for mean intake and 42-44% for high consumers.
Statement (National language(s))	As above	text	substance_statement_XX (instead of XX: national language; e. g. substance_statement_DE)	[...]
Statement References	References, e. g. the official statement	text	substance_references	https://www.bfr.bund.de/cm/343/reduzierung-der-aluminiumaufnahme-kann-

	from that the short statement is taken			moegliche-gesundheitsrisiken-minimieren.pdf
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Exposure assessment table (Optional)

Referring to the short statement, the underlying exposure assessments can be included as another optional information. This increases transparency by giving the end-users the information on which data the assessment of the short statement is based on.

The exposure assessment table contains descriptions of the analysed substances, age groups, production type (organic/conventional – if differentiated) and the exposure assessments, differentiated between mean and high intake, both lower bound (LB) and upper bound (UB).

Table aliases: substance_exposure

File format: .xls, .csv

Name	Description	Format	Aliases	Example
Substance Code	The unique identification code of the substance. The provided substance code should match with the code of the content data table.	Sequence of digits and/or letters	substance_id	AI
Age group English	Age group as a text	text	age_EN	adults, >18 years
Age group National language(s)	as above	text	age_XX (instead of XX: national language; e. g. age_DE)	[...]
Organic	Is the substance considered as organic.	Boolean value	organic	1 (True)/ 0 (false)
Exposure (LB, mean Intake)	Estimated exposure, calculated for mean intake, lower bound.	number	lower_bound_mean_intake	0,1792
Exposure (UB, mean Intake)	Estimated exposure, calculated for mean intake, upper bound.	number	upper_bound_mean_intake	0,2051
Exposure (LB, high Intake)	Estimated exposure, calculated for high intake, lower bound.	number	lower_bound_high_intake	0,4160
Exposure (UB, high Intake)	Estimated exposure, calculated for high intake, upper bound.	number	upper_bound_high_intake	0,4388
Unit	Unit of the specified exposures.	text	unit	mg kg ⁻¹ bw week ⁻¹

Contribution of food groups to exposure (Optional)

Additionally it is highly recommended to provide data regarding the contribution of food groups to dietary exposure of substances.

The Substance contribution table contains the substance codes, age groups, production type (organic/ conventional – if differentiated), codes of the food group and contribution of the food groups to dietary exposure (lower bound and upper bound).

Table aliases: substance_contribution

File format: .xls, .csv

Name	Description	Format	Aliases	Example
Substance Code	The unique identification code of the substance. The provided substance code should match with the code of the content data table.	Sequence of digits and/or letters	substance_id	AI
Age group	Age group as a text	text	age_EN	adults / >18 years
Age group National language(s)	as above	text	age_XX (instead of XX: national language; e. g. age_DE)	[...]
Organic	Is the substance considered as organic.	Boolean value	organic	1 (True), 0 (false)
Food Group Code	The unique identification code of the food group. Food can be coded after FoodEx2 or dataset-specific. The provided food group code should match with the code of the content data table.	Sequence of digits and/or letters	food_group_id	4
Contribution (LB)	Calculated contribution of individual food groups to dietary exposure (%), lower bound.	number (%)	lower_bound_contribution	19,7%
Contribution (UB)	Calculated contribution of individual food groups to dietary exposure (%), upper bound.	number (%)	upper_bound_contribution	17,6%

Appendix 7 – User Manuals Low-end user app: user assistance for End Users

HOME

Click here to open the menu panel and to change the app's language.

Type the name of the substance you're interested in.

Learn about the concentrations of the selected substance in foods.

Get a quick overview regarding population-based intake levels and their comparison to health-based reference values for the selected substance.

Get more information about the selected substance, reference values, intake levels, contribution of food groups to dietary intake and further literature.

Substance View: Aluminium, Al

Contents in foods

- Cocoa powder: 3.37 mg
- Fruit infusion (instant): 0.37 mg
- Coffee beverages: 0.18 mg
- Cappuccino: 0.18 mg
- Roibos infusion: 0.18 mg
- Tea beverages: 0.16 mg
- Fruit infusion: 0.02 mg
- Herbal tea: 0.02 mg

Food View: Cocoa powder

Amount [mg/100g]

Substance: Pb, Cu, Mn

Amounts: Pb (0.0), Cu (0.8), Mn (1.2)

Values and bars show the contents of the substances in the respective food. Select a food to learn about concentrations of selected substances in the food and compare them with other foods.

Substance View: Aluminium, Al

Further information

Basic nutritional/toxicological information

Contributors to dietary intake

Literature

Substance View: Aluminium, Al

Essential substance: YES / NO

Dietary reference value (DVB):

Tolerable upper intake level: 1 mg kg⁻¹ bw week⁻¹ (TWI)² (adults) 1 mg kg⁻¹ bw week⁻¹ (TWI)² (children)

Estimated intake/exposure

Bar chart: Average intake (0.5), High intake (0.8)

Show reference value: MAN, WOMAN

Learn more about health-based reference values and population-based estimated intakes.

Find out how different food groups contribute to dietary intake.

Click here for further information (links to references, websites).

Choose one or more population groups to compare the estimated intake with the respective health-based reference values.

SECTION: FOOD VIEW

Type the name of the food you're interested in or use the filter options.

Compare the concentrations of the selected food with the concentrations of all foods of the same food group.

Choose individual foods of the same food group to compare the concentrations with the selected food.

Choose up to five substances to learn more about their concentrations in the selected food.

Select a substance to learn more about its concentrations in foods, health-based reference values and estimated intakes.

SECTION: DATASET

